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SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT

INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry-Academia collaboration (IAC) mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation. It aims to build upon pre-existing IAC mechanisms such as EIT KICs and to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows to develop solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries. Of a highly digitalised nature, our project pilots the mechanism's two main components: a methodology developed by applying human-centred design principles and an online platform aimed at connecting stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and at supporting them throughout their co-creation journey.

The INDUSAC methodology provides the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform stands as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions. Through the experience of supporting at least 300 transnational co-creation teams throughout the project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components will be successively improved until the project ends, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. It is expected for INDUSAC to also create a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including at least 1000 companies, 3000 students and 300 researchers by project end. The INDUSAC counts with a strong interdisciplinary, cross-sectorial and geographically balanced partnership that counts with the needed expertise and network to achieve our project's goals.

ABSTRACT

This deliverable (D1.4 Methodology beta version) builds upon D1.3 - User Journey Maps and User Guidance (Rudolph et al., 2023b), and describes the workflow of the INDUSAC piloting, which has several phases. In the Planning phase, companies identify a challenge and students/researchers are made aware of the project opportunities. In the Onboarding phase, companies register on the INDUSAC platform and issue a Challenge. During the Search phase, students/researchers select appropriate Challenges, assemble co-creation teams and submit Motivation Letters, and the INDUSAC Evaluation Board and the companies carry out the selection of co-creation teams to solve their Challenges. During the Project phase, selected co-creation teams proceed with solving the Challenge with assistance from the company. INDUSAC will provide students, researchers and companies with tailored guidance packages to support their co-creation experience. Finally, during the Offboarding phase, co-creation projects are completed and both companies and students/researchers provide feedback on the process. The process ends when the company confirms the completion of the co-creation project (the submission of the solution to the Challenge) including the reporting duties, and researchers and students receive the INDUSAC certificate whereas participating student members of the co-creation teams are in addition eligible to receive funding up to 1,000 EUR gross per student (with a max of 3,000 EUR gross per team). Challenges and Motivation Letters are submitted continuously, with three cut-off dates at which collected Motivation Letters are reviewed and co-creation teams are selected to carry out the co-creation projects within four to eight weeks. The methodology also presents the Invitation to universities, Call for companies and Call for students and researchers, where terms and conditions for all participants are listed, including the aspects of geographical coverage, gender balance and internationalisation, status requirements, as well as confidentiality and intellectual property. The INDUSAC methodology will be successively improved until the project's end.

Keywords: INDUSAC, academia-industry cooperation, methodology, co-creation

LIST OF ACRONYMS

BCG	Boston Consulting Group
BIC	BYDGOSZCZ INDUSTRIAL CLUSTER TOOL VALLEY
CCIPB	PECS-BARANYAI KERESKEDELMI ES IPARKAMARA
CET	Central European Time
CHE	Chemistry
CIT UPC	UPC Technology Center
CUT	Cyprus University of Technology
CV	Curriculum vitae
ECA	European Court of Auditors
ECO	Economic Sciences
EIT	EIT Manufacturing East GmbH
ENG	Information Science and Engineering
ENV	Environment and Geosciences
EU	European Union
EUR	Euro
FAQ	frequently asked questions
FM	final milestone meeting
FSTP	financial support to third parties
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
IAC	Industry-academia collaboration
IBAN	international bank account number
ID	identification
INDUSAC	Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centred Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations
INNO	Innoget / INNOVAWIN 2006 SL
JSI	INSTITUT JOZEF STEFAN
KIC	knowledge and innovation community
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
KO	kick-off meeting
KPI	key performance indicator
LIF	Life Sciences
M	month
MAT	Mathematics
MS	milestone meeting
MSc	master of sciences

NACE	Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community (Nomenclature statistique des activités économiques dans la Communauté européenne)
NDA	non-disclosure agreement
NR	number
OLAF	European Anti-Fraud Office
PCA	Pre-defined collaborative approach
PhD	doctor of philosophy
PHY	Physics
SME	small-to-medium sized enterprise
SOC	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSH	social sciences and humanities
SWIFT	Society for Worldwide Interbank Financial Telecommunications
SWOT	Strengths weaknesses opportunities threats
UK	United Kingdom
VAT	value added tax

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I. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable (D1.4 Methodology beta version) describes the workflow of the INDUSAC piloting. It is intended to visualise the workflow as it is best considered by INDUSAC partners to the time given. The workflow may be refined throughout the project (for example, following a first round of issuing Challenges and receiving Motivation Letters), when further knowledge has been gained. The objective of this deliverable is to describe the process from inviting companies to issuing Challenges until the finalisation of the co-creation projects by the co-creation teams of students and researchers.

This document is structured as follows; Section 1 outlines the context. Section 2 explains the workflow with a stepwise description of each process step. Section 3 explains the definitions and roles within the co-creation process. Section 4 outlines the social sciences (SSH) aspects. Section 5 (the Annexes) provides the forms and templates.

1.1 About the INDUSAC project

INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry-Academia collaboration mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation. Its aim is to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows to develop solutions that address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries. Of a highly digitalised nature, the project will pilot the mechanism's two main components: a methodology (this deliverable) and an online platform aimed at connecting stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and at supporting them throughout their co-creation journey. The INDUSAC methodology will provide the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform will stand as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions. Through the experience of supporting at least 300 transnational co-creation teams throughout the project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components will be successively improved until the project end, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. It is expected for INDUSAC to also create a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including at least 1,000 companies, 3,000 students and 300 researchers by project end.

The aim of the INDUSAC project is (Objective 3):

- *Reaching at least **2,000 students and researchers registered from 30 research organisations**, 100 companies, and at least 3 KICs and 15 industrial clusters offering long-term access to at least 10,000 SMEs and covering at least 14 member states, with a total minimum user representation of 60% from widening countries.*
- *Achieving a minimum average of 7 connections per month from all users and an average time on the site of 5 minutes.*

- *Achieving a minimum of 3,000 members by project end, covering the sectors and cross-cutting areas addressed.*

It is one of INDUSAC's goals (Objective 4) *to set up at least 300 co-creation projects.* Achievement of this is verified and measured by counting each started and completed pilot (co-creation) project within the set timeframe of the project dedicated to piloting. In total (Objective 7), *at least 1,000 students and researchers will be supported in real business environments throughout the project's lifetime.*

1.2 About the INDUSAC Co-creation Process

The objectives of co-creation are to promote and push the use of the INDUSAC platform for cross-border EU-wide matching challenges of companies and solutions by students/researchers. The platform will play a dual role. On the one hand, it will provide a digital matchmaking and networking space that will enable the connection between companies and co-creation teams. On the other hand, it will stand as a virtual co-creation arena for students, researchers and company representatives to work together in solving the latter's industrial challenges. The process will establish the co-creation system as a catalyst for integration of academia in business practices and technical solutions.

In order to ensure process transparency, participation and funding decisions will be based on clearly described rules and procedures. All applicants (students and researchers) will receive adequate feedback on the outcome of the evaluation of their Motivation Letter.

II. INDUSAC Call Conception

The following sections describe the workflow for the co-creation process companies and students/researchers undergo with the support of INDUSAC partners. This workflow starts with issuing a Challenge by a company. The process ends when the company confirms the completion of the co-creation project (the submission of the solution to the Challenge) including the reporting duties, and researchers and students receive the INDUSAC certificate whereas students also receive funding. The process flow will be reassessed during the project's lifetime (using questionnaires for students and researchers and companies) and may be subject to modifications.

INDUSAC will provide students, researchers and companies with tailored guidance packages to support their co-creation experience based on user journey maps and guidance developed through INDUSAC, as well as a set of Pre-defined Collaborative Approaches (PCAs) which are self-contained project types aimed at providing companies models of project typologies to be adapted to the specific needs of the Challenge being addressed.

2.1 INDUSAC Process Overview

The INDUSAC process involves (i) companies, (ii) students and researchers, and (iii) INDUSAC project partners. For companies, students and researchers, several phases can be distinguished (Table 1) and are shown schematically in Figure 1. Separate documents guiding companies and students/researchers are presented in deliverable D1.3 - User Journey Maps and User Guidance (Rudolph et al., 2023b).

Table 1 : Phases of the INDUSAC process and relevant activities for companies and for students/researchers.

	For Companies	For Students/Researchers
Planning Phase	identifying a Challenge	raising awareness
Onboarding Phase	registration, posting a Challenge	/
Search Phase	selection of co-creation teams	choosing an appropriate Challenge and assembly of a co-creation team; registration
Project Phase	assisting students/researchers in solving the Challenge	solving the Challenge
Offboarding phase	feedback on the process	feedback on the process

Figure 1 : Simplified outline of the INDUSAC process.

2.1.1 Timeline of the Co-creation projects

Publication of the call / invitation for universities: May 2023 (already published)

Publication of the call for companies: October 2023

Publication of the call for students and researchers: November 2023

Three cut-off dates for students and researchers to submit Motivation Letters:

1. Wednesday, 31.01.2024 at 17:00 CET,
2. Thursday, 30.05.2024 at 17:00 CET and
3. Wednesday, 30.10.2024 at 17:00 CET

Duration of individual co-creation projects: four to eight weeks.

Timeline for the first cut-off date (31.01.2024).

- Until 07.02.2024, INDUSAC coordinator reviews the received Motivation Letters and rejects those that are not in English, in Latin alphabet.

- Until 23.02.2024, companies make final selections. For rejected Motivation Letters companies use the pre-defined justifications.
- Until 07.03.2024, students sign the FSTP declaration at which time the co-creation project begins.
- Until 02.05.2024, all co-creation teams submit final reports (summary, deliverables as defined in PCAs, upskilling questionnaire, testimonial).
- Until 09.05.2024, companies review the Summary and Deliverables.
- Until 15.05.2024, the Evaluation Board confirms the list of students from the co-creation teams to be funded.
- Until 15.06.2024, all students from the list receive funding

Timeline for the second cut-off date (30.05.2024).

- Until 07.06.2024 INDUSAC coordinator reviews the received Motivation Letters and rejects those that are not in English, in Latin alphabet.
- Until 24.06.2024, companies make final selections. For rejected Motivation Letters companies use the pre-defined justifications.
- Until 08.07.2024, students sign the FSTP declaration at which time the co-creation project begins.
- Until 02.09.2024, all co-creation teams submit final reports (summary, deliverables as defined in PCAs, upskilling questionnaire, testimonial).
- Until 09.09.2024. companies review the Summary and Deliverables.
- Until 15.09.2024, the Evaluation Board confirms the list of students from the co-creation teams to be funded.
- Until 15.10.2024, all students from the list receive funding.

Timeline for the third cut-off date (30.10.2024).

- Until 07.11.2024, INDUSAC coordinator reviews the received Motivation Letters and rejects those that are not in English, in Latin alphabet.
- Until 23.11.2024, companies make final selections. For rejected Motivation Letters companies use the predefined justifications.
- Until 07.12.2024, students sign the FSTP declaration at which time the co-creation project begins.

- Until 01.02.2025, all co-creation teams submit final reports (summary, deliverables as defined in PCAs, upskilling questionnaire, testimonial).
- Until 08.02.2025, companies review the Summary and Deliverables.
- Until 14.02.2025, the Evaluation Board confirms the list of students from the co-creation teams to be funded.
- Until 14.03.2025, all students from the list receive funding.

2.2 Invitation for Universities to Issue Letters of Support

Public universities and public research institutions will be invited to join the INDUSAC community by signing a Letter of Support. By providing Letters of Support, universities and research institutions show their willingness to promote INDUSAC opportunities among their students and researchers.

The aim is to engage with at least 15 organisations at the start of the open call and reach at least 30 at the end of it. The duration of the Open Call for Universities and Research Centres is 18 months, from M9 (May 2023) to M26 (October 2024). The universities and research centres that will sign the Letters of Support, will receive INDUSAC promotional material in order to promote among their students and researchers the participation in the competitions of co-creation teams. Students and researchers will be able to express interest, join a co-creation team and submit their solutions to Challenges any time from M15 (November 2023) till M26 (October 2024).

A list of participating universities and research centres will be published on the INDUSAC website.

Students/researchers will become aware of INDUSAC through different communication channels - social media (Twitter and YouTube), media relations and promotional materials (such as flyers and rollups at different events). Information about INDUSAC will also be available in LinkedIn groups and posts concerning the project, as well as in university press releases or traditional or specialised media (such as articles published by the INDUSAC partners, or scientific publications concerning the project).

The invitation and the Letter of Support are in Annexes 1 and 2.

2.3 Call for Companies

Companies will be invited to cooperate in the INDUSAC project by issuing Challenges for students and researchers to solve them within the co-creation teams in four to eight weeks.

The call for companies is in Annex 3.

2.3.1. Registration of Companies on the INDUSAC Platform

Prior to issuing the Challenge, companies will register (sign-up) on the platform and provide certain information (Annex 4). The company can create a company profile and an account for each company representative. To do this, they create an appropriate user account (company account or company representative account) and fill in all the required information. The mandatory fields will be publicly visible on the platform. To successfully register, a company must accept the terms and conditions outlined in the Call for companies (Annex 3) and the Registration Form (Annex 4).

2.3.2. Issuing a Challenge

The company will issue a Challenge to which students/researchers will submit solution proposals, ie. Motivation Letters. A company designates a representative responsible for issuing a Challenge by filling in the PCA template, revising the Challenge if necessary, and ultimately publishing the Challenge.

Companies will provide the Challenges based on nine types of Pre-defined Collaboration Approaches (PCAs), which are compiled in the Deliverable D1.2 (Rudolph et al., 2023a). PCAs will target nine general areas of potential Challenge: (1) developing a robust product, (2) market analysis, (3) marketing strategy, (4) developing a digital platform prototype, (5) developing service/product ideas based on target groups, (6) developing service/product ideas based on trends, (7) developing a business plan, (8) developing a virtual prototype, and (9) developing a business model. The PCAs will, among other information, include the following:

- title of the Challenge
- description of the problem with additional explanations of key terms
- expectations - what does the company expect in terms of solution, impact and type of collaboration with the co-creation team
- desired co-creation team profile - which skills are desired for solving the Challenge
- a submission agreement to formalise the process

To issue a Challenge, a company clicks on "Add Challenge" on the INDUSAC platform. INDUSAC provides nine differently-themed templates to create a Challenge. The templates are designed to guide the company in providing students and researchers, who will be solving the Challenge, with all the information they need. It is also an opportunity for the company to check that the Challenge has been fully thought through. All Challenges will be publicly available and have to include only non-confidential information.

The company defines the maximum number of co-creation teams that it can work with in the PCA. The company will make sure to keep the number of co-creation teams

manageable as there will be milestone meetings at which a company representative should be present to make the Challenge a success.

When a company submits a Challenge it gets an automatic notification that the text is being reviewed by the INDUSAC administrators, and the company will be notified about the progress (see Annex 12). Likewise, the company is notified when the Challenge is published.

Company Challenge submissions will be a continuous process (for a detailed timeline, see Section 2.1.2).

2.3.3. Revision of Issued Challenges

INDUSAC will receive the company's Challenge and check it for eligibility. If any information is missing or something is not clear, the company receives an email from the INDUSAC administrators and can revise the Challenge until it is completed.

2.3.4. Publishing of Challenges

Once the revisions are completed (or there are no revisions necessary) and the company confirms the final version, clicking on the appropriate button changes the status of the Challenge to "published", and the company receives a notification (Annex 12.2).

After the Challenge has been published, the company has the option to host a Challenge presentation. This gives the company the opportunity to have a first meeting with potential co-creation teams interested in their Challenge.

2.4 Call for Students and Researchers (financial support to third parties)

2.4.1. Opening the Call

The Call for Students and Researchers will open in November 2023. The INDUSAC project consortium will publish the open call on the project's homepage (<https://indusac.eu/>). The call will also be published on the Horizon Europe Funding and Tenders portal from the European Commission under the Horizon Europe standards, therefore ensuring transparency, equal treatment, absence of conflict of interest, and confidentiality. All project partners will in addition disseminate the call opening via their own dissemination channels. The call will be sent also to universities and research organisations that signed INDUSAC letters of support.

The call will have three cut-off dates, ie. 31.01.2024, 30.05.2024 and 30.10.2024, for a detailed timeline, see Section 2.1.2 and the call text (Annex 5).

2.4.2. Call for Students and Researchers Section on the INDUSAC website

There will be a dedicated call section for students and researchers on the INDUSAC website www.indusac.eu with the full details of the call, the screenshots of application

forms (online available on the INDUSAC platform) and the FAQ section. Assistance and further information will also be available at the email address indusac@ijs.si.

2.4.3. Horizon Europe Funding & Tenders Portal

According to the [European Commission Guidance note](#) on financial support to third parties under Horizon Europe, all calls for third parties and all calls that are implemented by third parties (co-creation teams) must be published on the Funding & Tenders Portal, and on the INDUSAC website.

2.4.4. Registration of students/researchers on the INDUSAC platform

Prior to submitting Motivation Letters, students and researchers will register (sign-up) on the INDUSAC platform (each student/researcher creates their own appropriate user account) and provide certain information (Annexes 6 and 7).

Students and researchers complying with the terms and conditions in the Call for students and researchers (Annex 5) are eligible to participate in co-creation projects.

2.4.5. Putting together a Co-creation Team / Matchmaking

A student/researcher selects a Challenge through the INDUSAC website. Clicking on a Challenge provides more information.

Once students/researchers have chosen one (or more) Challenge(s), they can start putting together a co-creation team. To do so, they can go (recommended but not necessary) on the third-party platform Slack (slack.com). The link to the Slack channel for the concrete Challenge will also be visible in the Challenge posting. In this Slack channel one can express interest and list their skills necessary to solve this Challenge. In this channel, one can also read what other interested parties (students/researchers) have posted. By going through the provided information of every interested person, or engaging in chats, one can start to find a co-creation team.

If students wish to form a co-creation team with others they met on slack (or elsewhere), they all sign up for the platform individually (if they have not yet done so). If they decide to use slack, they can create a slack channel for them as a team themselves where they can start getting to know each other and prepare their Motivation Letter - which is the letter each team has to submit to express their interest in taking over a challenge. Each co-creation team (created on the platform) automatically gets an ID. To submit the Motivation Letter on the platform one member clicks the button to submit a motivation on the challenge page. There is a field where the co-creation team leaders can insert all the e-mail addresses of fellow team members (the e-mails with which their accounts on the platform were created). Each co-creation team member gets an e-mail notification where they confirm participation in a co-creation team and accepts terms and conditions. In case one member did not yet have an account on the platform registered to the e-mail address, they get an invitation to join the platform. Additionally, the team members can also be invited via e-mail by their colleagues or via notification from the platform.

2.4.6. Submission of the Proposal (Motivation Letter)

Once all co-creation team members are registered on the platform, a co-creation team can apply for a Challenge. To do so, the co-creation team needs to submit a common Motivation Letter (ie. a single Motivation Letter per co-creation team, see Annex 8). In this document, a co-creation team must explain why they are motivated to solve this Challenge, what skills they might have to solve this Challenge, and how it will be addressed. The co-creation team will be encouraged to fill in the fields as accurately as possible as these data are important as evaluation criteria (Impact score, Excellence score, Implementation score, and Transversal criteria - see the Call - Annex 5).

Motivation Letters may also outline solutions to the Challenge as well as descriptions of academic and technical ability to provide the solutions if the team already has an idea. It is not necessary to have an idea already at this state. The Motivation Letter form will clearly indicate the name of the Challenge, the evaluation fields to fill-in, and it will also allow for uploading supporting documents such as CVs, images and video clips. Motivation Letters need to be submitted through the platform. Motivation Letters submitted by any other means will not be evaluated.

In the next step, the co-creation team must select the co-creation team leader. This person will be the one who will submit the Motivation Letter (and thus apply for the Challenge). The co-creation team leader will upload the co-creation team's Motivation Letter for the Challenge and add all co-creation team members to the Challenge in the application/Motivation Letter template. To apply, the co-creation team leader accepts the legal terms and conditions and applies for the Challenge. The other members of the co-creation team will receive notification for joining the co-creation team to submit the Motivation Letter (Annexes 8 and 13.2) and must also accept the legal terms and conditions. All co-creation team members must confirm the Motivation Letter through the link in the received notification (Annex 13.3) before the cut-off date.

If there are fields missing, the Motivation Letter will not be submitted and a warning will pop up indicating the specific element of non-compliance (marked with red colour). If the co-creation team does not meet the INDUSAC eligibility criteria, as set out in the Call for Students and Researchers, verification of which will be integrated into the platform's functionalities, they will not be able to submit the Motivation Letter. In that case, the specific element of non-compliance will be marked with red colour on the registration form.

Motivation Letters may be submitted anytime during the open Call. The time recorded by the platform, as submission time of the Motivation Letter, will be the official one. Late Motivation Letters will not be admitted. After the closing of a cut-off date no additions or changes to received Motivation Letters will be considered. Students and researchers can participate in up to three different co-creation teams (and contribute to up to three different Motivation Letters to up to three different Challenges).

2.4.7. Acknowledgement of Receipt of Motivation Letter

Upon submission of each Motivation Letter, students/researchers will receive a notification acknowledging successful submission (Annex 13.3).

2.4.8. Closing the Call

There will be three cut-off dates at which co-creation teams submit Motivation Letters. The first one will be 31.01.2024, as described above. Applications received after 17:00 CET on the respective cut-off day cannot be taken into consideration anymore. The second cut-off date will be on 30.05.2024. The last cut-off date will be on 30.10.2024. With this date the call for the students and researchers is closed.

2.5 Evaluation of Motivation Letters

All Motivation Letters and related data, knowledge and documents are treated in confidence.

The evaluation process includes handling the Motivation Letters after the submission and approval or non-approval (rejection) of the received Motivation Letters by the companies.

All students/researchers receive adequate feedback on the outcome of the evaluation of their Motivation Letter.

All companies with Challenges will get detailed guidelines on the evaluation of solutions (Annex 11).

2.5.1. Preselection of Motivation Letters by the INDUSAC Evaluation Board

INDUSAC coordinator reviews the received Motivation Letters and rejects those that are not in English and in Latin alphabet.

INDUSAC partners will use the platform to send the company the links to the Motivation Letters on the platform for further selection (Annex 12.3).

2.5.2. Evaluation and Feedback from Evaluators (INDUSAC and Company)

The company evaluates (and for justification uses pre-prepared explanations) the Motivation Letters through the template (Annex 10) and makes final selections based on selection criteria (Annex 10). This evaluation is concluded up to one month after the cut-off date.

In case of rejection, the application process of the respective co-creation teams will stop (and no costs will be reimbursed).

The co-creation teams receive a notification over the INDUSAC platform (Annex 13.4). If the response is positive, the process continues and leads to the initiation of the project.

The evaluation timeline is given in Section 2.1.2. The evaluation form is given in Annex 10.

All co-creation teams are notified about the approval or rejection of their Motivation Letter (Annex 13.4) with justification. In case of approval students will receive an invitation to sign a FSTP declaration (see the Call for Students and Researchers), and be provided with a template (see Call for Students and Researchers). The declaration needs to be signed by all co-creation student team members. Researchers don't sign the FSTP Declaration.

2.6 Implementation of Co-creation Projects

Upon signing of the FSTP declaration for a co-creation project by students, the co-creation team and the company are notified through the platform (Annexes 12.4 and 13.6) and implementation of the co-creation projects can start immediately. A project must not take longer than eight weeks to finalise.

If the company requires any additional contracts to sign (e.g. NDA) with students and researchers, this is arranged outside of the INDUSAC project. For detailed terms and conditions see the Call for students and researchers.

2.6.1. Clarity and Satisfaction Survey for Students / Researchers at the Beginning and at the End of Co-creation Project Implementation

After the co-creation team members receive information about approval of their Motivation Letter, they fill out a questionnaire - a brief survey to evaluate their skill level (Annex 14). Questions for students and researchers are intended to provide valuable information on clarity of, and satisfaction with the co-creation process, in order to be able to improve, if any, methodology elements for the 2nd Call based on the 1st Call, and elements for the 3rd Call based on the 2nd Call.

2.6.2. Implementation

In the Challenge, a company will provide co-creation teams with clear expectations about the co-creation team's skills necessary to carry out the tasks, their expected work results, and a level of the company's involvement. In general, the co-creation teams will work on the Challenge independently of the company (except from regular milestone meetings). INDUSAC will provide the co-creation teams with a list of deliverables, methods and tools for the Challenge. In addition, the co-creation teams will be provided with a planned timeline / mentoring plan (to-do list) to complete the Challenge (Annex 19). These instructions will be customised for each PCA type.

Throughout the process, the co-creation teams should have milestone meetings with the company.

The results are reported in a Co-Creation Implementation Report through the INDUSAC platform (Annex 9).

The implementation of the co-creation project will take place in several phases: a first (kick-off) meeting between the company and the co-creation team, one or more milestone meetings, and a final meeting, over the course of four to eight weeks. Students/researchers will study the details and methods of the Challenge and investigate the company in more detail. Students/researchers will present a first set of results at the first milestone meeting. Further work will then focus on possible shortcomings and refine the working process accordingly, to ensure that the solution develops in the desired direction. At the final milestone meeting students/researchers will present a final solution and receive feedback from the company. The feedback will be incorporated into the students/researchers' deliverables before the final submission.

Below is an example timeline of a co-creation process. The process consists of a kick-off meeting (KO), followed by up to four project phases with corresponding milestone meetings (MS1, MS2). In each project phase, the co-creation teams work on different tasks to help them prepare the solution. The process concludes with a final milestone meeting (FM) where the co-creation team presents its results. The Challenge ends with submission of the results to the company and the company's approval.

Figure 2 : An example timeline of a co-creation process

2.6.3. Monitoring of the Co-creation Projects

Throughout the process the company and the co-creation teams may be approached by the INDUSAC Mentoring Board to discuss if they are progressing as planned and if they need any additional guidance. A selection of projects (20-30 during the first 6 months, and 15 during the last 9 months of piloting) will be closely monitored by INDUSAC partners in order to identify possible improvements to be implemented on the mechanism.

The selection of the monitored project will be done based on:

- Geographical distribution
- PCA type distribution
- Date of implementation start

Specific steps in the implementation of the monitoring:

- For monitoring duties, the respective member of the Mentoring Committee will monitor co-creation projects based on a Mentoring plan.
- The INDUSAC Mentoring Committee member establishes contact with the company and the co-creation team (eg. via e-mail) to check on the progress and verify that the co-creation project is being carried out as agreed at the kick-off meeting.
- The INDUSAC Mentoring Committee member fills out the monitoring plan (the member of the Mentoring Committee checks the status of concrete activity and insert possible comments).

The monitoring report follows the To-Do lists / mentoring plans corresponding to individual PCAs; the Mentoring Committee records in the To-Do List the progression of major milestones and any problems that may occur, over the co-creation project periods outlined in Figure 2. For each milestone, the Mentoring Committee may check and advise on elements such as clarity of INDUSAC guidelines, adherence to deadlines, timely delivery of results, and communication between the company and the co-creation team. Mentoring Committee members give the company and the co-creation team further guidance on the next steps and finalisation of the results.

On a more general level, the Monitoring Committee will be monitoring the performance of the co-creation projects on the INDUSAC platform and bring to the attention of the INDUSAC consortium any major irregularities or digressions from the work plan, so as to find rapid solutions.

Apart from interaction with companies/co-creation teams, INDUSAC will monitor the efficiency of the platform and user experience (Objective 2) with the aim of:

- *Measuring the up-time of the platform when running aiming for at least 99.9% uptime in a 24/7 regime (INNO).*
- *Measuring less than 1 visit to any Help function for each 10 user sessions logged on the online platform (INNO).*
- *Measuring less than 1 error ticket for 100 user sessions (INNO).*
- *Zero unsolved issues regarding privacy, labour, tax or any other legal framework in the EU (INDUSAC coordinator).*
- *Scoring above 4.0 out of 5 on a Likert scale questionnaire on user experience of the online platform and the offline modalities of the platform (as measurable from the questionnaires) (INDUSAC coordinator).*

2.6.4. Troubleshooting

In case of conflict between companies and students/researchers from the co-creation project the INDUSAC project coordinator takes on a neutral role and mediates between

them. Every conflict needs to be described in writing and be available to everyone involved. Finding a solution for the conflict at an earlier exit point is prioritised to considering an exit at any of the subsequent exit points.

2.6.5. Exits

In the co-creation process, exit points of companies, students and researchers are foreseen only in case of Force Majeure.

In case of an exit where deliverables are missing, or the solution is not fulfilling minimal requirements in quality or quantity, reimbursement to students is not possible. For details see Annexes 3 and 5 (Call for Companies and Call for Students and Researchers).

2.6.6. Reporting

2.6.6.1. Reporting by students and researchers

Once the co-creation project implementation is completed, the co-creation team submits an implementation report (see the Call for students and researchers).

The implementation report will include:

- Deliverables (according to a specific PCA) - uploaded on the platform by the co-creation team leader in the document section of the Challenge.
- Questionnaire “after” (Annex 15) - filled out by each member of the co-creation team
 - Upskilling questionnaire
 - Testimonial
 - Short description of the project results
 - Inclusiveness statement
 - Compliance with the ethics requirement

which will be submitted via the platform.

As per the [Horizon Europe Work Programme](#), selected outcomes of the calls will be published without delay, including a description of third-party projects, the date of the award, the duration, and the legal name and country of the students/researchers.

Questions for students/researchers after submission of the final report

(Annex 15; comparing answers to these questions before the start of project and after its completion will provide a satisfaction score, as set out in Objective 1 of the INDUSAC project, aiming for a minimum average satisfaction score of 3.8 out of 5)

Some of the questions in the questionnaire provide data for checking the level of achievement of Objectives 5 and 7:

- *Demonstration of the feasibility of running the IAC mechanism with less than 3,000 EUR per co-creation team.*
- *At least 70% of students and researchers participating reporting at least one core professional transversal and entrepreneurial skill having been significantly developed by participating in the piloting of the INDUSAC IAC.*
- *At least 70% of SMEs reporting that the solution(s) delivered by the co-creation quick intervention were highly relevant to their company and contributed to overcoming the challenge that was identified by them (and which was accepted by the programme as being suitable).*
- *At least 80% of students and SME staff stating that it is likely or highly likely they would recommend participation in such a programme to their peers.*
- *An improved set of skills in students and researchers by at least 30% compared to before the beginning of the project, allowing them to rapidly expand their skill set in a short period of time and to find themselves more prepared for the business environment.*

2.6.6.2. Reporting by companies

The company will provide feedback on the INDUSAC process through the INDUSAC platform that will include:

- Deliverable quality assessment (which were submitted by the co-creation team - for details see 2.6.7; Annex 11)
- Questionnaire “after” (Annex 16)
 - Questionnaire
 - Testimonial

The company may choose to write a letter of recommendation for the co-creation team members.

2.6.7. Evaluation of Solutions

The Evaluation Team comprised of the Evaluation Board (1 INDUSAC member) and a company representative (already described in 2.6.6.2.) will evaluate the solution of the Challenge proposed by the co-creation team (according to the criteria in the Calls for Students and Companies) that will give the final score of each co-creation project and a list of FSTP student recipients (Annex 11).

After this step, students will receive payment from INDUSAC to the bank account they indicated during the project initiation. Students and researchers will receive a certificate of participation from INDUSAC through the platform.

2.6.8. Financial Support for Students

A dedicated budget of financial support to third parties (FSTP) is available in a total amount of 900,000 EUR as a lump sum. The total amount per co-creation team for student members of the co-creation team is 3,000 EUR gross, out of which up to 1,000 EUR gross per student member. The amount will be transferred as a lump sum to the student after the solution for the Challenge is confirmed by the Evaluation Team.

Only students within the co-creation teams are the money (FSTP) recipients. Neither researchers nor companies are receiving FSTP.

All FSTP payments to the students will be done by the INDUSAC coordinator. The INDUSAC coordinator will oversee and monitor the FSTP towards students based on the FSTP declarations signed once co-creation teams are selected. Three cut-off dates for payments will be set up (no more than five months after the cut-off date in the call for students and researchers to submit the Motivation Letter for the Challenges). The amount shall not be in any case higher than 3,000 EUR gross per co-creation team (i.e. 1,000 EUR gross per student as a lump sum). A single student/researcher will be able to participate in up to three Motivation Letters. A single student receives up to 1,000 EUR gross for each co-creation project and is limited up to 3,000 EUR gross if the student participates in three co-creation projects.

The template for the FSTP declaration is given in the Call for Students and Researchers.

2.7 Follow-up on Co-creation Projects

2.7.1. Follow-up Challenges

If a company publishes a Challenge before the first cut-off date, it can create a follow-up Challenge for the second or third cut-off date. This can be, for example, a continuation of the Challenge based on the last solution.

For a timeline see Section 2.1.1.

III. Definitions and Roles of INDUSAC Boards and Committees within the Co-creation Process

3.1 INDUSAC Evaluation Board

The Evaluation Board that is composed of the INDUSAC WP Leaders and additional evaluators, will review the rejected solutions of the Challenge proposed by the co-creation teams (according to the criteria in the Calls) that will give the final score of each co-creation project and a list of FSTP student recipients.

The Evaluation Board is composed of appointed partner representatives and coordinated by the INDUSAC coordinator.

3.2 INDUSAC Evaluation Team

The Evaluation Team is composed of the Evaluation Board (one INDUSAC member) and a company representative, both of which are included in evaluation for a particular case / challenge / solution.

3.3 Inclusiveness Board

The Inclusiveness Board is composed of appointed partner representatives and coordinated by the INDUSAC coordinator.

Function: the board is responsible for verification of inclusiveness, gender equality, and other ethical issues.

3.4 Mentoring Committee

The Mentoring Committee is composed of appointed INDUSAC partner representatives and coordinated by the INDUSAC coordinator.

Function: the committee is in charge of carrying out a quick monitoring of the performance and quality of selected projects, providing an assessment that will be used for improving the INDUSAC methodology, including the platform.

IV. INDUSAC's human-centred approach on the co-creation process

INDUSAC's co-creation process involves individuals from different backgrounds that come together to collaboratively create and innovate. In such processes, prioritising human-centred aspects becomes essential to ensure the process is inclusive, ethical and meaningful for students, researchers and companies, as well as for the European society. INDUSAC, through its methodology, considered several aspects to ensure the appropriate human-centred approach, including gender dimension and social sciences and humanities integration.

- **Inclusivity:** INDUSAC's gender and geographical balance requirements ensure diversity and representation among the participants, encouraging participants from different genders, ethnicities, and backgrounds. The Inclusiveness Board ensures an inclusive environment where participants feel respected and empowered to contribute with their unique perspectives. The Evaluation Board through the transversal criteria is able to consider inclusivity aspects on the selection of Motivation Letters.
- **Gender dimension:** The support material, specifically designed for each PCA, provides guidance to address specific needs, and perspectives of individuals of different genders. Gender-sensitive research methods, such as gender-disaggregated data collection or gender-focused interviews, can be employed to gather insights and inform the co-creation process. INDUSAC's team formation requirements ensure gender balance by promoting diverse gender representation. The INDUSAC Inclusiveness Board is responsible for creating a safe and respectful environment for open dialogue and valuing gender-specific insights.
- **Interdisciplinarity:** INDUSAC team creation process involves participants from a wide range of disciplines, including social sciences and humanities. Incorporating diverse perspectives, fostering holistic problem-solving, and generating innovative solutions that consider both the human element and the broader societal implications.
- **User Perspective:** PCAs are designed to place the end-users at the center of the co-creation process. Support material provides tools to understand their needs, desires, and pain points through research methods.
- **Collaboration:** INDUSAC mechanism is based on collaboration, cooperation, and co-learning among participants. Each PCA, in which challenges are based, proposes a process timeline and a to-do list (Mentoring plan), designed to promote the culture of sharing knowledge, skills, and experiences. Support material includes activities that foster mutual understanding and learning.
- **Iterative feedback:** PCA's proposed process timeline incorporates at least three feedback sessions between students/researchers and company representatives

throughout the co-creation process. This methodology encourages participants to provide constructive criticism, suggestions, and insights at various stages. Iterations and refinement of ideas based on the feedback received ensure continuous improvement and successful outcomes.

- Ethical considerations: INDUSAC upholds the highest ethical standards and ensures responsible practices throughout the co-creation process as described in the Call for companies and the Call for students and researchers. The INDUSAC mechanism respects privacy, confidentiality, and consent and considers the ethical implications of any data collected and used.

V. FINAL REMARKS

While the INDUSAC consortium will make sure to include clear instructions for navigating the project, and clear eligibility conditions for participating, at appropriate points, such as the INDUSAC website and platform, wide dissemination and engagement with companies and co-creation teams for assistance may be necessary for successful matchmaking. INDUSAC partners therefore share the understanding that the methodology and its elements described in the previous sections represent a coherent workflow, and commit to supporting students, researchers, companies, and each other, in successful piloting.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable represents the basis for one of the two major pillars of the INDUSAC project, namely, the project's methodology. As such, the beta version contains all the operational elements necessary for the execution of the project – the phases, steps, definitions, and supporting documentation for the upcoming open calls within the project. The beta version will be improved based on feedback from a workshop resulting in the Methodology pre-validation report (upcoming deliverable D1.5) and the improvement will manifest as the operational version, INDUSAC Methodology (upcoming deliverable D1.6), which will itself go through revisions and improvements (including feedback from piloting and in-depth monitoring) until the end of the project.

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ANNEX 1 : Call for Universities on the INDUSAC Website

Universities are invited to promote the INDUSAC project among their students via the INDUSAC web page: <https://indusac.eu/invitation-to-participate-in-an-exciting-new-project-aimed-at-strengthening-the-collaboration-between-industry-and-academia/>

The Quick Challenge-Driven, Human-Centred Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUStry-Academia Collaborations (INDUSAC) is a HORIZON EUROPE project that aims to develop and validate an Industry-Academia Collaboration mechanism.

Within the project, the INDUSAC project partners will facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows the development of solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries^[1].

Students and researchers will create international co-creation teams of at least three members that will solve companies' Challenges within four to eight weeks. INDUSAC has a budget of 900,000 EUR gross intended for student members of co-creation teams, where mini-grants of 3,000 EUR gross will be distributed among student members of each co-creation team (ie. up to 1,000 EUR gross per student). By solving companies' Challenges, students will get international working experiences, collaborative experiences by working with students and researchers from different countries, and transversal and entrepreneurial skills (communication, negotiation, results orientation, responsibility, creativity, planning skills, and analytical thinking, among others), access to companies from the EU and associated countries, references, and a certificate of participation from INDUSAC. By participating in co-creation teams, researchers will gain companies' and students' contacts, letters of recommendation from industry partners, and a certificate of participation from INDUSAC.

In support of this project, we would kindly ask your organisation to sign the attached Letter of Support. This letter will show your willingness to promote the INDUSAC opportunities among your students and researchers and will serve as a foundation for future collaboration.

If you agree to sign the attached Letter of Support, please add the official letterhead/logo of your organisation and send it back to us, together with the logo of your organisation.

Your logo will be displayed on the project's website (www.indusac.eu) among the logos of the other supporting organisations.

INDUSAC partners will provide you with all the necessary promo materials (mostly e-format) about INDUSAC opportunities that you can distribute among your students and researchers.

No financial obligations shall take place.

We would be honoured to gain your organisation's support for this project, and we would be happy to provide you with more information about the project and its goals. If you are interested in learning more, please do not hesitate to contact us at indusac@ijs.si.

ANNEX 2 : Letter of Support by Universities

LETTER OF SUPPORT

Place, date: _____

To: Partners of the INDUSAC consortium

With this letter, we would like to express the support of our organisation,

_____ (*insert the organisation name*), for the
HORIZON EUROPE project "INDUSAC" (INDUSAC has received funding from the European
Union's Horizon Europe Programme under the Grant Agreement No. 101070297).

We confirm our willingness to promote the INDUSAC opportunities among our students
and researchers.

We are looking forward to future collaboration.

Name of Legal Representative (eg. Rector/Director)

Signature and stamp

ANNEX 3 : Call for companies

INDUSAC OPEN CALL FOR COMPANIES

Programme: Horizon Europe Framework Programme

Call: A HUMAN-CENTRED AND ETHICAL DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL AND INDUSTRIAL TECHNOLOGIES 2021 (HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01)

The call is managed by EU project [INDUSAC](#) under Horizon Europe programme. The Horizon Europe project INDUSAC, aims to financially support short-term (4-8 weeks) research collaborations between academia (students and researchers) and industry (companies), in solving company Challenges. Financial support in the form of financial support to third parties (FSTP) is given solely to student members of the co-creation teams.

Expected outcome: 300 successful collaborations between industry and academia.

Companies are invited to provide Challenges to receive solutions from the co-creation teams (students and researchers) within four to eight weeks after the selection process of teams is finished.

Opening date: October 2023

Deadline model: single-stage, three cut-off dates

Deadline for submitting a Challenge: Companies issue Challenges continuously from the call opening date up to one of cut-off dates:

- 15.12.2023,
- 15.04.2024,
- 15.09.2024.

Eligibility

Companies established in the EU as well as companies established in associated countries will be eligible to issue Challenges: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, The Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Albania, Armenia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Faroe Islands, Georgia, Iceland, Israel, Kosovo, Moldova, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Norway, Serbia, Tunisia, Turkey, Ukraine, Morocco, UK.

There are no restrictions on the sector, type, or size of a company to issue a Challenge (startups and large enterprises may apply as well as SMEs).

English is the official language of all INDUSAC documents using the Latin alphabet.

Application and implementation process

Step 1 - Registration on the INDUSAC Platform

The registration process (Annex 4) allows a company to create a profile and publish a Challenge on the INDUSAC platform. During the registration, the company is invited to provide certain information about the company, and verify that a company accepts the terms and conditions of this Call.

Step 2 - Issuing a Challenge on the INDUSAC Platform

On the INDUSAC platform, the company selects from nine different Challenge templates: (1) developing a robust product, (2) market analysis, (3) marketing strategy, (4) developing a digital platform prototype, (5) developing service/product ideas based on target groups, (6) developing service/product ideas based on trends, (7) developing a business plan, (8) developing a virtual prototype, and (9) developing a business model. The Challenge templates - among other information - ask for the following:

- title of the Challenge,
- description of the problem with additional explanations of key terms,
- expectations - what does the company expect in terms of solution, impact and type of collaboration with the co-creation team,
- desired co-creation team profile - which skills are desired in solving the Challenge,
- the maximum number of co-creation teams that the company can work with,
- a submission agreement to formalise the process.

Challenges, together with the company's name, county and website will be publicly available and have to include only non-confidential information.

The Challenges issued before 15.12.2023 will be eligible for receiving possible solutions by the co-creation teams by May 2024. The Challenges issued before 15.04.2024 will be eligible for receiving possible solutions by the co-creation teams by September 2024. The Challenges issued after 15.04.2024 will be eligible for receiving possible solutions by the co-creation teams by February 2025.

Step 3 - Selection of co-creation teams

Within this step the company selects the most suitable co-creation teams through selection of their Motivation Letter. Motivation Letters will be evaluated based on Team's motivation, Excellence score, Impact score, Team and resources, and Transversal criteria (Table 2).

Evaluation criteria for evaluating the Motivation Letters (from co-creation teams):

(1). TEAM'S MOTIVATION (5%)

- Personal motivation: reflection of a team's enthusiasm for taking on the challenge.
- Did the team introduce the team members? (yes/no)

- Do their strengths and abilities adequately explain the reason why they are suitable? (yes/ no)
- Will they be able to work together as a team? Do they already have team cohesion?

(2). EXCELLENCE (30%):

- Soundness of the approach and credibility of the proposed methodology, according to the expectations of companies.
- Are the efficiency and quality of work related to the challenge well explained?

(3). IMPACT (30%):

- Do you believe the co-creation team will find a solution that can be successful on the market?
- To what level will the potential solution be innovative in regards to the existing solutions on the market (incremental improvement, radical improvement, breakthrough innovation, ...)? Focus on the creativity of how the team predicted their future success and not on a potential solution they might have proposed.
- Has a co-creation team already found out about the companies' competition and how they will try to get to a differentiated solution?
- How important will the project be for the company and how well did the team foresee the impact?

(4). TEAM AND RESOURCES (30%):

- Transversal, entrepreneurial and leadership skills, technical expertise, co-creation teams' ability to take a concept from ideas to market, and their capacity to carry through their ideas and understand the dynamics of the market they are trying to tap into.
- Does the team have specific resources that qualify them as a team specifically to find an excellent solution?
- Is the foreseen time consumption (hours/team member) for the co-creation project sensibly aligned with the project structure, and fitting within the four to eight weeks time frame?

(5). TRANSVERSAL CRITERIA (5%):

- Does a co-creation team have ideas how to include 'Environment and low carbon economy contribution', 'Equal Opportunities, Gender balance & Diversity', 'Inclusiveness' or 'Social Impact' within their way to a solution for the challenge?

Table 2 : Criteria and scoring system for evaluating Motivation Letters.

Evaluation criteria	Weighting	Max scoring in points	Max scoring with weighting
Motivation	5 %	5	0,25
Excellence	30 %	5	1,5
Impact	30 %	5	1,5
Team and resources	30 %	5	1,5
Transversal criteria	5 %	5	0,25

Motivation Letters that receive a score 0 in one or more criteria (1 Excellence, 2 Impact, 3 Team and Resources, 4 Transversal criteria) will be automatically rejected.

Accepted Motivation Letters need to receive all together at least 50% of available scores. A ranking list will be prepared. INDUSAC will provide companies with pre-defined justifications for rejecting Motivation Letters.

Step 4 - Implementation of co-creation projects

INDUSAC will provide the co-creation teams with a list of deliverables, methods and tools for the Challenge. In addition, the co-creation teams will be provided with a planned timeline / mentoring plan (to-do list) to complete the Challenge. These instructions will be customised for each Challenge type.

Throughout the process, the company should have the kick-off, at least one milestone meeting and the feedback meeting with each co-creation team.

Monitoring of the Co-creation Projects by INDUSAC

Throughout the process, the company and the co-creation teams may be approached by the INDUSAC Mentoring Committee to discuss if they are progressing as planned and if they need any additional guidance.

On a more general level, a Monitoring Committee will be monitoring performance of the co-creation projects on the INDUSAC platform and bring to the attention of the INDUSAC consortium any major irregularities or digressions from the work plan, so as to find rapid solutions.

Step 5 - Reporting

The company provides feedback on the INDUSAC process through the INDUSAC platform (Annex 11) that will include:

- Deliverable quality assessment of the solution submitted by the co-creation team

The company evaluates the deliverable quality of the submitted Solution (30% of the overall score), Business performance indicators and Technical performance indicators (60% of the overall score), Deadline Compliance (10% of the overall score, which is given automatically if the Solution is submitted on time) of the submitted Solution.

- Questionnaire “after” (Annex 16)
 - Questionnaire
 - Testimonial

Timeline

For receiving Motivation Letters in February 2024 and Solutions in May 2024, companies need to submit Challenges by 15.12.2023 (first cut-off date) so as to have them published by 31.12.2023.

For receiving Motivation Letters in June 2024 and Solutions in September 2024, companies need to submit Challenges by 14.04.2024 (second cut-off date) so as to have them published by 30.04.2024.

For receiving Motivation Letters in November 2024 and Solutions in February 2025, companies need to submit Challenges after 15.12.2023 and up to 15.09.2024 (third cut-off date) so as to have them published by 30.09.2024.

Terms and Conditions for companies

Number of Challenges issued

A company may issue more than one Challenge.

Compliance with European Council Implementing Decision (on Hungarian entities)

The company confirms that it is not in conflict with the European Council Implementing Decision 2022/2506 in regards to funding Hungarian entities, which stipulates that legal commitments must not be entered into with any public interest trusts established on the basis of the Hungarian Act IX of 2021 or any entity maintained by such a public interest trust. This applies as of 16.12.2022 for as long as the measures are in place. The company confirms that it is not associated with any of the affected entities listed on the Hungarian national legislation website (<https://njt.hu/jogszabaly/2021-9-00-00>).

Confidentiality

The company confirms that the text, data and other content of the Challenges is non-confidential.

For cases where companies wish to share with the selected co-creation teams its confidential information, they are advised to sign a Non-Disclosure Agreement with the co-creation team before the start of the co-creation project.

INDUSAC partners who have access to the co-creation projects and co-creation results, have signed the Statement on Non-Disclosure of Information and Impartiality (Annex 17) and all non-public and personal data will be treated in confidence.

Intellectual Property

The company confirms that the material shared by the company representatives is owned by the company they represent and / or they have acquired the rights for their usage.

Should the cooperation between students/researchers and the company give rise to any form of intellectual property (for example, a patent application), division of ownership of intellectual property rights (based on individual parties' contributions), the type of intellectual property, and management of said intellectual property, shall be defined in a separate agreement on joint inventions. The parties (company, co-creation team) agree to the following provisions:

- On the basis of the undisputed fact that an invention presents a result of joint collaboration of student/researcher and the company and that student/researcher and the company were involved in the process of creation and development of the invention, the invention shall be considered as a joint invention of student/researcher and the company.
- Any intellectual property developed prior to the solving of a Challenge belongs to the party that developed it.
- Procedures such as registration and maintenance of the intellectual property shall be coordinated by the company.
- Students must follow the guidelines set by the company in regards to intellectual property disclosure and ownership; they may sign a statement waiving their economic intellectual property rights, by which they are exempt from any financial obligations towards protection of said intellectual property rights (such as, for example, preparation, registration / filing, processing, expansion, and maintenance fees); they may opt to retain authorship rights only, in which case they remain co-authors on the invention but receive no material benefits.

- Researchers must follow appropriate invention disclosure legislation, which may include disclosing the invention to their employer and subsequently transferring intellectual property rights to the employer.
- Regardless of status and intellectual property rights transfers, student/researcher retains the right to be listed as co-author on the invention.

The parties (company, student, researcher) agree that each party, individually or together with the remaining party, may use the invention for the purpose of its own research, without restrictions and without any obligation to remunerate the other party in any form or manner. The parties agree that the results of the co-creation project, except the INDUSAC requirements, will not be published, commercialised or otherwise allowed to be used by third parties without written agreement by all parties.

Long-term relevance of Challenges

For all issued Challenges, the companies acknowledge that Motivation Letters will be evaluated at three cut-off dates and that their Challenge, regardless of how soon it was issued, must still be relevant for the first upcoming cut-off date.

Ethics

The action must be carried out in line with:

- the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity).
- applicable EU, international and national law, including the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its Supplementary Protocols.

Based on the Horizon Europe Ethic Self-Assessment guidance ([European Commission, 2021](#)) the company must ensure that the activities under the action do not include the following:

- human embryonic stem cells
- human embryos
- human foetal tissues/cells
- cause harm to the environment, animals, or plants
- military applications
- malevolent / criminal / terrorist abuse

The company may decide to reject a proposed Motivation Letter. The company assures that any rejections of Motivation Letters will be based solely on the quality of the Motivation

Letters (following the INDUSAC evaluation criteria) and not be affected by the co-creation teams' gender or citizenship/residency.

If a co-creation team has provided draft solutions or solution proposals in applying to a Challenge, but ends up rejected, the company commits to discarding the rejected proposal without any further use of the solutions proposed therein.

Values

All parties must commit to and ensure the respect of basic EU values (such as respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and human rights, including the rights of minorities).

Conflict of interests

The company must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the co-creation project could be compromised for reasons involving family, emotional life, political or national affinity, economic interest or any other direct or indirect interest ('conflict of interests').

The company confirms that it is not giving preferential treatment in regards to Motivation Letters / Solutions based on the applicant's professional or personal connections with the company and that approval is based solely on the quality of the Motivation Letters / Solutions.

Disputes and exits

The parties (companies, students and researchers) agree that they will conclude in writing any amendments to any existing arrangements, and will endeavour to resolve any disputes regarding this arrangement in a peaceful manner. In the event that the parties cannot resolve the dispute individually, the INDUSAC coordinator shall mediate over the dispute.

In the co-creation process exit points of companies, students and researchers are foreseen only in case of Force Majeure.

Keeping records and supporting documents

The company acknowledges that it can substantiate the proper implementation of the action by records and other supporting documentation that will be produced upon request or in the context of checks, reviews, audits and investigations.

The company can provide written proof, if required from INDUSAC partners, European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA), European Commission, European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF), Court of Auditors (ECA) or other competent EU institutions.

Communication, Dissemination And Visibility

Visibility — European flag and funding statement

Unless otherwise agreed with the INDUSAC, communication activities of the parties (company, students, researcher) related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities or major results implemented under the INDUSAC must acknowledge INDUSAC and EU support and display the INDUSAC logo, European flag (emblem) and include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement No 101070297”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. Graphic guide to use EU logo is available here:

<http://publications.europa.eu/code/en/en-5000100.htm>

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency (European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA)) is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains:

“The content of this [insert appropriate description, e.g. report, publication, conference, infrastructure, equipment, insert type of result, etc.] represents the author’s view only and is his/her sole responsibility. The European Commission and the Agency (European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA)) do not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains.”.

ANNEX 4 : Registration form for companies

REGISTRATION FORM ON THE PLATFORM for companies

Marked with ** for data that will be visible on the public part of the platform without the login

- ****Name of the company**
- Address of the company
- ****Country** (drop down menu of eligible countries: all EU countries and all Associated countries)
- VAT number
- ID number
- Name of legal representative
- E-mail of legal representative (must be an official organisation email rather than general or personal address, such as Gmail or similar)
- ****Website**
- Name of contact person
- E-mail of contact person
- Nr. of employees (tick suitable box: 0-10, 11-50, 50-250, 250-1,000, more than 1,000) also for statistical purposes
- [NACE code](#) (for statistical purposes): A - Agriculture, forestry and fishing, B - Mining and quarrying, C - Manufacturing, D - Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply, E - Water supply; sewerage; waste management and remediation activities, F - Construction, G - Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles, H - Transporting and storage, I - Accommodation and food service activities, J - Information and communication, K - Financial and insurance activities, L - Real estate activities, M - Professional, scientific and technical activities, N - Administrative and support service activities, O - Public administration and defence; compulsory social security, P - Education, Q - Human health and social work activities, R - Arts, entertainment and recreation, S - Other services activities, T - Activities of households as employers; undifferentiated goods - and services - producing activities of households for own use, U - Activities of extraterritorial organisations and bodies
- Tick the box: I confirm that the information provided in the registration process is complete, reliable and true.
- Tick the box: we accept all Terms and Conditions as set out in the Call for Companies
- Tick the box: I give my permission to preserve and share information given in this questionnaire strictly for the purposes of the INDUSAC project (company data, such as specific contacts, to be shared strictly within the INDUSAC consortium and non-

personal data to be used for the purposes of statistical analyses, the results of which may be published)

ANNEX 5 : Call for Students and Researchers

INDUSAC OPEN CALL FOR STUDENTS AND RESEARCHERS

Programme: Horizon Europe Framework Programme

Call: A HUMAN-CENTRED AND ETHICAL DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL AND INDUSTRIAL TECHNOLOGIES 2021 (HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01)

The call is managed by EU project INDUSAC under Horizon Europe programme. The Horizon Europe project INDUSAC, aims to financially support short-term (4-8 weeks) research collaborations between academia (students and researchers) and industry (companies), in solving company Challenges. Financial support to third parties (FSTP) is given solely to student members of the co-creation teams.

Expected outcome:

- 300 successful collaborations between industry and academia,
- Supported co-creation projects shall include at least 50 % female representation.
- 60% members of the co-creation teams must be from Widening Countries.
- Distribution of 900.000 EUR gross for FSTP to student members of the co-creation teams,

Students and researchers are invited to create co-creation teams and solve companies' Challenges within 4-8 weeks.

Opening date: November 2023

Deadline model: single-stage, three cut-off dates

Deadline for submitting a Motivation Letter:

- 31.01.2024,
- 30.05.2024
- 30.10.2024

The Motivation Letter from a co-creation team is considered submitted once all co-creation team members confirm participation in the co-creation team and confirms the terms and conditions.

Eligibility

Eligible countries: In accordance with the Horizon Europe Call, students and researchers in each co-creation team must come from EU Member States (Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, The Netherlands, Spain, Sweden), in particular Widening countries (Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia; source) or Associated Countries (1. Albania, 2. Armenia, 3. Bosnia and Herzegovina, 4. Faroe Islands, 5. Georgia, 6. Iceland, 7. Israel, 8. Kosovo, 9. Moldova, 10. Montenegro, 11. North Macedonia, 12. Norway, 13. Serbia, 14. Tunisia, 15. Turkey, 16. Ukraine, 17. Morocco, 18. UK), **as indicated by their citizenship or residency.**

Eligibility for Students.

- Students must study at public universities during the entire duration of the activity (from the co-creation team establishment until one month after the final report of the co-creation team is confirmed).
- An individual student will be able to participate in more than one co-creation team but in maximum three Motivations.

Eligibility for Researchers.

- Researchers must be employed at a public research organisation during the entire duration of the activity (from the co-creation team establishment until one month after the final report of the co-creation team is confirmed).
- An individual researcher will be able to participate in more than one co-creation team but in maximum three Motivations.

Eligibility of Co-creation Teams.

- The co-creation team must have at least three and up to six members.
- Co-creation team members must be from at least three different EU Member States or Associated Countries.
- The co-creation team has to be gender balanced (operationally, gender balance entails selecting at least two different gender options (Male, Female, Would rather not say)).
- Each co-creation team must include at least one student, ie. no co-creation team may comprise exclusively researchers.
- At least 60% members of the co-creation team must be from Widening Countries.

English is the official language of all INDUSAC documents using the Latin alphabet.

Budget: up to 1,000 EUR gross per student (lump sum), up to 3,000 EUR gross per co-creation team wherein only students are eligible for funding; 900,000 EUR gross in total, for supporting 300 projects.

Application and implementation process

Step 1 - Registration

Prior to submitting Motivation Letters, students and researchers register (sign-up) (Annexes 6 and 7) on the INDUSAC platform (each student/researcher creates their own appropriate user account) and provides certain information.

Step 2 - Putting together a co-creation team

A student/researcher selects a Challenge. Once students/researchers have chosen a Challenge, they start putting together a co-creation team. Each co-creation team (created on the platform) automatically gets an ID. They may use the platform Slack (slack.com) or another communication channel of their choice.

Students already registered on the INDUSAC platform can invite students not yet registered, to join a co-creation team via e-mail. Once a co-creation team has been assembled, members can create their own channels and discuss their ambitions, goals, and further details. In this chat, they also start preparing their Motivation Letter.

Step 3 - Motivation Letter submission

Once all co-creation team members are registered on the platform, a co-creation team can apply for a Challenge. The co-creation team must select the co-creation team leader, who submits a common Motivation Letter (ie. a single Motivation Letter per co-creation team) that is confirmed by all co-creation team members before the final submission. After the closing of a cut-off date, no additions or changes to received Motivation Letters will be considered.

Motivation Letters (Annex 8) need to be submitted through the INDUSAC platform. Motivation Letters submitted by any other means will not be evaluated.

After the cut-off date the company selects co-creation teams based on evaluation criteria and instructions for Motivation letter (Annex 8, Table 3).

Evaluation criteria for evaluating the Motivation Letters (from co-creation teams):

(1). TEAM'S MOTIVATION (5%)

- Personal motivation: reflection of a team's enthusiasm for taking on the challenge.
- Did the team introduce the team members? (yes/no)
- Do their strengths and abilities adequately explain the reason why they are suitable? (yes/ no)
- Will they be able to work together as a team? Do they already have team cohesion?

(2). EXCELLENCE (30%):

- Soundness of the approach and credibility of the proposed methodology, according to the expectations of companies.
- Are the efficiency and quality of work related to the challenge well explained?

(3). IMPACT (30%):

- Do you believe the co-creation team will find a solution that can be successful on the market?
- To what level will the potential solution be innovative in regards to the existing solutions on the market (incremental improvement, radical improvement, breakthrough innovation, ...)? Focus on the creativity of how the team predicted their future success and not on a potential solution they might have proposed.
- Has a co-creation team already found out about the companies' competition and how they will try to get to a differentiated solution?
- How important will the project be for the company and how well did the team foresee the impact?

(4). **TEAM AND RESOURCES (30%):**

- Transversal, entrepreneurial and leadership skills, technical expertise, co-creation teams' ability to take a concept from ideas to market, and their capacity to carry through their ideas and understand the dynamics of the market they are trying to tap into.
- Does the team have specific resources that qualify them as a team specifically to find an excellent solution?
- Is the foreseen time consumption (hours/team member) for the co-creation project sensibly aligned with the project structure, and fitting within the 4-8 weeks time frame?

(5). **TRANSVERSAL CRITERIA (5%):**

- Does a co-creation team have ideas how to include 'Environment and low carbon economy contribution', 'Equal Opportunities, Gender balance & Diversity', 'Inclusiveness' or 'Social Impact' within their way to a solution for the challenge?

Table 3 : Evaluation criteria and scoring system for Motivation Letters.

Evaluation criteria	Weighting	Max scoring in points	Max scoring with weighting
Motivation	5 %	5	0,25
Excellence	30 %	5	1,5
Impact	30 %	5	1,5
Team and resources	30 %	5	1,5
Transversal criteria	5 %	5	0,25

Motivation Letters that receive a score 0 in one or more criteria (1 Excellence, 2 Impact, 3 Team and Resources, 4 Transversal criteria) will be automatically rejected.

Accepted Motivation Letters need to receive all together at least 50% of available scores.

Step 4 - Before the start of the co-creation project implementation

Students

Once the co-creation project is approved each student member of the co-creation team fills out the Questionnaire (Annex 14), provides certain data (bank details, etc) and signs the FTSP declaration electronically.

Researchers

Once the co-creation project is approved, each research member of the co-creation team fills out the Questionnaire (Annex 14).

Step 5 - Implementation of co-creation projects

Students and researchers must solve companies' Challenges within four to eight weeks.

INDUSAC will provide the co-creation teams with a list of deliverables, methods and tools for the Challenge. In addition, the co-creation teams will be provided with a planned timeline / mentoring plan (to-do list) to complete the Challenge.

Throughout the process, each co-creation team should have the kick-off, at least one milestone meeting, and the feedback meeting with the company.

Monitoring of the Co-creation Projects by INDUSAC

Throughout the process the company and the co-creation teams may be approached by the INDUSAC Mentoring Committee to discuss if they are progressing as planned and if they need any additional guidance.

On a more general level, a Monitoring Committee will be monitoring performance of the co-creation projects on the INDUSAC platform and bring to the attention of the INDUSAC consortium any major irregularities or digressions from the work plan, so as to find rapid solutions.

Step 6 - Reporting

The results are reported in a Co-Creation Implementation Report through the INDUSAC platform (Annex 9) latest on 02.05.2024 (for the first cut-off date), 02.09.2024 (for the second cut-off date) or 01.02.2025 (for the third cut-off date).

The implementation report will include:

- Deliverables (according to a specific Challenge type) - uploaded on the platform by the co-creation team leader in the document section of the Challenge.
- Questionnaire “after” - filled out by each member of the co-creation team
 - Upskilling questionnaire
 - Testimonial
 - Short description of the project results
 - Inclusiveness statement
 - Compliance with the ethics requirementwhich will be submitted via the platform.

Evaluation of Solutions

Each criterion will be scored from 0 to 10 and the weight of each one of these criteria, in the final score, will be as follows: Deliverable quality of submitted Solution (30% of the overall score); Business performance indicators and Technical performance indicators (60% of the overall score), Deadline Compliance (10% of the overall score, which is given automatically if the solution is submitted on time) of the submitted Solution.

Students from co-creation teams with solutions scoring above the threshold (7 points) will receive payment.

Timeline

- 31.01.2024 first cut-off date (deadline) for Motivation Letter submission
- 07.03.2024 deadline for students with approved Motivation Letters to sign a FSTP declaration (Annex 18), at which time the co-creation project begins
- 02.05.2024 deadline for submission of final reports by co-creation teams for the first cut-off date
- 15.06.2024 all students with approved reports receive funding
- 30.05.2024 second cut-off date (deadline) for Motivation Letter submission
- 08.07.2024 deadline for students with approved Motivation Letters to sign a FSTP declaration (Annex 18), at which time the co-creation project begins
- 02.09.2024 deadline for submission of final reports by co-creation teams for the second cut-off date
- 15.10.2024 all students with approved reports receive funding.
- 30.10.2024 second cut-off date (deadline) for Motivation Letter submission
- 07.12.2024 deadline for students with approved Motivation Letters to sign a FSTP declaration (Annex 18) at which time the co-creation project begins
- 01.02.2025 deadline for submission of final reports by co-creation teams for the third cut-off date
- 14.3.2025 all students with approved reports receive funding.

Financial support to third parties

Financial support to third parties (FSTP) based on a Lump sum is given solely to student members of the co-creation teams up to 1,000 EUR gross per student.

Students receive financial support to third parties after approval of the Implementation report on a Solution (as described in Step 6 - Reporting of this Call).

INDUSAC coordinator shall transfer the funds to students within thirty (30) days from the date of the approval of the implementation report on a Solution / final confirmation from the INDUSAC Evaluation Board.

Terms and Conditions for students and researchers

Compliance with European Council Implementing Decision (on Hungarian entities)

The students/researchers confirm that they are not in conflict with the European Council Implementing Decision 2022/2506 in regards to funding Hungarian entities, which stipulates that legal commitments must not be entered into with any public interest trusts established on the basis of the Hungarian Act IX of 2021 or any entity maintained by such a public interest trust. This applies as of 16.12.2022 for as long as the measures are in place. The students / researchers confirm that they are not associated with any of the affected entities listed on the Hungarian national legislation website (<https://njt.hu/jogszabaly/2021-9-00-00>).

Confidentiality

For cases where students/researchers wish to share with the selected company their confidential information they are advised to sign a Non-Disclosure Agreement with the company before the start of the co-creation project.

INDUSAC partners who have access to the co-creation projects and co-creation results, have signed the Statement on Non-disclosure of Information and Impartiality (Annex 17) and all non-public and personal data will be treated in confidence.

Intellectual Property

Should the cooperation between student/researcher and the company give rise to any form of intellectual property (for example, a patent application), division of ownership of intellectual property rights (based on individual parties' contributions), the type of intellectual property, and management of said intellectual property, shall be defined in a separate agreement on joint inventions. The parties agree to the following provisions:

- On the basis of the undisputed fact that an invention presents a result of joint collaboration of student/researcher and the company and that student/researcher and the company were involved in the process of creation and development of the invention, the invention shall be considered as a joint invention of student/researcher and the company.
- Any intellectual property developed prior to the solving of a Challenge belongs to the party that developed it.
- Procedures such as registration and maintenance of the intellectual property shall be coordinated by the company.
- Students must follow the guidelines set by the company in regards to intellectual property disclosure and ownership; they may sign a statement waiving their economic intellectual property rights, by which they are exempt from any financial obligations towards protection of said intellectual property rights (such as, for example, preparation, registration / filing, processing, expansion, and maintenance

fees); they may opt to retain authorship rights only, in which case they remain co-authors on the invention but receive no material benefits.

- Researchers must follow appropriate invention disclosure legislation, which may include disclosing the invention to their employer and subsequently transferring intellectual property rights to the employer.
- Regardless of status and intellectual property rights transfers, student/researcher retains the right to be listed as co-author on the invention.

The parties (company, student, researcher) agree that each party, individually or together with the remaining party, may use the invention for the purpose of its own research, without restrictions and without any obligation to remunerate the other party in any form or manner. The parties agree that the results of the co-creation project, except the INDUSAC requirements, will not be published, commercialised or otherwise allowed to be used by third parties without written agreement by all parties.

Ethics

The action must be carried out in line with:

- the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity).
- applicable EU, international and national law, including the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its Supplementary Protocols.

Based on the Horizon Europe Ethic Self-Assessment guidance (European Commission, 2021) the co-creation team must ensure that the activities under the action do not include the following:

- human embryonic stem cells
- human embryos
- human foetal tissues/cells
- cause harm to the environment, animals, or plants
- military applications
- malevolent / criminal / terrorist abuse

Values

All parties must commit to and ensure the respect of basic EU values (such as respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and human rights, including the rights of minorities).

Conflict of interests

Students/researchers must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the co-creation project could be compromised for reasons

involving family, emotional life, political or national affinity, economic interest or any other direct or indirect interest ('conflict of interests').

By applying for the Call, students and researchers confirm that neither they nor their close family ties (spouse, domestic or non-domestic partner, child, sibling, parent etc.) are in business or scientific rivalry or professional hostility with the company behind the challenge they are submitting the Motivation Letter for.

Students further confirm that they are not receiving double financing for any of their activities within the INDUSAC project, ie. challenge solving activities within the co-creation team will not be funded from other sources except the INDUSAC financial support for third parties.

Applicants receiving financial support cannot be affiliated to any of the consortium partners, for example as consortium partner's board members or employees, with the exception of students employed for performing services unrelated to the challenge.

Disputes and exits

The parties (students, researchers, companies) agree that they will conclude in writing any amendments to any existing arrangements, and will endeavour to resolve any disputes regarding this arrangement in a peaceful manner. In the event that the parties cannot resolve the dispute individually, the INDUSAC coordinator shall mediate over the dispute.

In the co-creation process exit points of companies, students and researchers are foreseen only in case of Force Majeure.

Keeping records and supporting documents

The students/researchers acknowledge that they can substantiate the proper implementation of the action by records and other supporting documentation that will be produced upon request or in the context of checks, reviews, audits and investigations.

The students/researchers can provide written proof, if required from INDUSAC partners, European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA), European Commission, European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF), Court of Auditors (ECA) or other competent EU institutions.

Promotion

The members of the co-creation teams agree to provide statements / testimonials / experiences that can be published on the project website together with parts of the Challenge, through INDUSAC media and in project partners media.

Co-creation teams are given an option to have the INDUSAC communication team prepare a success story / a good practice story based on the co-creation team's project and results.

Communication, Dissemination And Visibility

Visibility — European flag and funding statement

Unless otherwise agreed with the INDUSAC, communication activities of the parties (company, students, researcher) related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities or major results implemented under the INDUSAC must acknowledge INDUSAC and EU support and display the INDUSAC logo, European flag (emblem) and include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement No 101070297”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. Graphic guide to use EU logo is available here:

<http://publications.europa.eu/code/en/en-5000100.htm>

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency (European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA)) is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains:

“The content of this [insert appropriate description, e.g. report, publication, conference, infrastructure, equipment, insert type of result, etc.] represents the author’s view only and is his/her sole responsibility. The European Commission and the Agency (European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA)) do not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains.”.

ANNEX 6 : Registration Form for Students

REGISTRATION FORM ON THE PLATFORM for students

Data needed when a student/researcher creates an account **(all the data is automatically inserted in the FSTP Declaration the students sign with INDUSAC):**

Mandatory fields marked with * are for the data that is visible to others after the login into the platform

- Name*
- Family name*
- Address
- Citizenship or residency (drop-down menu of the eligible countries) *
- Gender (tick: Male or Female or Would rather not say) *
- E-mail
- Month / year of study start – visible only to admin and for automatic verification of eligibility
- Foreseen month and year of study end (Students must study at public universities during the entire duration of the activity (from the co-creation team establishment until one month after the final report of the co-creation team is confirmed) – visible only to admin and for automatic verification of eligibility
- Name of public university where you study *
- Country of the university *
- Website of the university
- Mark your area of study:
 - Chemistry (CHE)
 - Social Sciences and Humanities (SOC)
 - Economic Sciences (ECO)
 - Information Science and Engineering (ENG)
 - Environment and Geosciences (ENV)
 - Life Sciences (LIF)
 - Mathematics (MAT)
 - Physics (PHY)
- Tick the box: I confirm that the information provided in the registration process is complete, reliable and true.
- Tick the box: we accept all Terms and Conditions as set out in the Call for Students and Researchers.
- Tick the box: I give my permission to preserve and share information given in this questionnaire strictly for the purposes of the INDUSAC project (personal data to be shared strictly within the INDUSAC consortium and non-personal data to be used for the purposes of statistical analyses, the results of which may be published).

ANNEX 7 : Registration Form for Researchers

REGISTRATION FORM ON THE PLATFORM for researchers**Marked with * for the data that is visible to others after the login into the platform**

- Name *
- Family name *
- Citizenship or residency (drop-down menu of the eligible countries)*
- Gender (tick Male or Female or Would rather not say) *
- E-mail (organisation email, no gmails or similar)
- Name of public research organisation where you work *
- Website of their employer *
- Mark your area of research:
 - Chemistry (CHE)
 - Social Sciences and Humanities (SOC)
 - Economic Sciences (ECO)
 - Information Science and Engineering (ENG)
 - Environment and Geosciences (ENV)
 - Life Sciences (LIF)
 - Mathematics (MAT)
 - Physics (PHY)

- Tick the box: I confirm that the information provided in the registration process is complete, reliable and true.
- Tick the box: we accept all Terms and Conditions as set out in the Call for Students and Researchers.

Tick the box: I give my permission to preserve and share information given in this questionnaire strictly for the purposes of the INDUSAC project (personal data to be shared strictly within the INDUSAC consortium and non-personal data to be used for the purposes of statistical analyses, the results of which may be published).

ANNEX 8 : Motivation Letter Form

Challenge Title

Posted by company name 🚩 Responsive company name Project Size Range 1,000 EUR gr./s Deadline for submission country

name start writing the name of your team (up to 250 characters)

Add your team mates here (use one field for each member, up to 50 characters in each field):

@yourself	@teammate 3	@teammate 6
@teammate 1	@teammate 4	@teammate 7
@teammate 2	@teammate 5	@teammate 8

how does this field work

Text to be implemented behind "how does this field work":
 To add your teammates, write: @Team_mate_Name. After submitting the motivation, your teammates have to confirm their participation in an e-mail they get after you submit the motivation. The motivation can only be evaluated once all team members accepted their invitation to participate in the e-mail.

Describe your team's motivation (up to 5000 characters):

Describe your team motivation in your own words. You should include why you as a team are most suitable to find a great solution for this challenge in collaboration with the industry partner. You can use this field to give a quick introduction to all the team members and let everybody state their personal motivation for this challenge. The conclusion should answer why you as a team are well prepared to solve this challenge.
 Example Conclusion: We as a team will find a great solution together since we not only come from different countries but we also study three very different degrees which will help us to think out of the box. Jane studies mechanical engineering and has a lot of experience with building physical prototypes. Tim is in his third year of an architecture bachelor's. He knows a lot about different materials, and has also been building prototypes since his first semester. Melanie studies corporate law and works in her free time for an NGO. We see ourselves as qualified not only to find an innovative solution but also to visualize it through a prototype. Furthermore, we will focus on finding a sustainable and durable solution that can be used in all countries. To make sure it fits with the different countries' regulations, Melanie uses her knowledge from a European corporate law class.

How will you address the following aspects (you may respond to all the criteria if possible) (up to 5000 characters):

Excellence: How will your team reach an excellent solution for this challenge? Why is your team one that can propose a solution that might become a real innovation?

Impact: Why do you believe your team will find a solution that can be successful on the market? To what level will your solution be innovative in regards to the existing solutions on the market (incremental improvement, radical improvement, breakthrough innovation, ...)? You may also describe what you already found out about the companies' competition and how you are trying to get to a differentiated solution. Do you already have ideas about how a solution to this challenge might not only solve the challenge but tackle a respective structural problem? How important will the project in your opinion be for the company? Will the solution be implementable also in other sectors?

Team and Resources: Demonstrate your transversal, entrepreneurial and leadership skills, your ability to take a concept from ideas to market, and your capacity to carry through your ideas and understand the dynamics of the market you are trying to tap into. Do you have specific resources that qualify you as a team specifically to find an excellent solution? Do you plan a visit to the companies' premises within the duration of the project? Do you plan any other travel (national or international; e.g., visiting a library, visiting a teammate, visiting a prototyping centre etc.)? How much time (hours/team member) do you plan to invest in this project?

Transversal criteria: Do you have ideas to include 'Environment and low carbon economy contribution', 'Equal Opportunities, Gender balance & Diversity', "Inclusiveness" or 'Social Impact' within your way to a solution for the challenge? If yes you may describe here how or why you are planning to do so.

Optional: If you already have an idea for a solution for this challenge, please briefly describe it here. Note: filling this field is optional (up to 5000 characters)

Description of your proposal

What should I include in this field?

Describe your proposal clearly, explaining what your product, technology, process, procedure, service or project is about without disclosing any confidential information not properly protected.

Describe the idea you have for solving this challenge as clearly as you can. It might include which technology you plan on using, procedures you believe solve the challenge, services or other details you came already up with in your team. If applicable please make sure you are not disclosing any confidential information.

This should be the text behind "What should I include in this field":
If you already came up with a potential solution and want to tell it to the company, you may do so here. It does not mean that you have to stick to this solution you have proposed here. If you come up with a different solution during the process, that is just normal.

Commercial Information

Intellectual property status

Add attachments

About you

Your complete profile will be included with your solution proposal. Review your information below.

[Team Leader profile]

Attachments

Drag & Drop your files here

Add pictures and other visuals to increase the description of your solution proposal.

Please upload your resume and, if needed, further documents concerning your idea for a solution. Possible formats: PDF, JPG, DOC, AVI, MPG4, XLS

Please be aware that the motivation will only be processed after submission, if all linked team members confirm their participation. An automated e-mail will be sent to every team member after you submit the motivation.

ANNEX 9 : Template for Co-creation Implementation Report

To be filled out by each member of the co-creation team.

Co-Creation Implementation Report	
Title of the Challenge	
Team Leader	
Team Member	
Team Member	
Start of project	(date)
End of project	(date)
<p>Short description of the project results. Please provide a short description of the project results and a short description of your personal contribution (five sentences total). Note that the description will be published on the INDUSAC website and on the EU platform so please don't include classified information.</p>	
<p>List of Deliverables prepared and uploaded on the platform</p>	
<p>Inclusiveness statement (explain in a few sentences how your solution is inclusive, ie. not excluding any groups of individuals in terms of gender, race, nationality, etc.)</p>	
Upskilling, clarity and satisfaction questionnaire	Annex 14

Testimonial: please provide a short testimonial, e.g. a letter or written statement of recommendation of something given or done as an expression of esteem, admiration, or gratitude. See two examples below:

"The company that issued the Challenge is active in the services sector. Due to a low number of employees and a busy schedule, it is a Challenge for them to find time to think out-of-the box. Within the INDUSAC co-creation project team, we not only got an opportunity to solve a real-life company problem and provide ideas for improved services but also got experience in international cooperation with fellow students and researchers. We would be happy to participate in similar initiatives in the future!"

"I learned about the INDUSAC at the university where I study. Then I checked the INDUSAC website and there were several Challenges from companies. Three Challenges were really interesting, I joined one co-creation team and we successfully submitted a Motivation Letter. For the first time I was able to be a member of an international co-creation team and worked with a company from France. I was able to contribute my ideas and knowledge. This was really a valuable experience."

ANNEX 10 : Template for Evaluation: Motivation Letters

Title of Challenge:

Company:

Co-creation Team:

Criteria (same for INDUSAC Evaluation Board and for companies):

Table 4 : Criteria and scoring system for evaluating Motivation Letters.

Evaluation criteria	Weighting	Max scoring	Max scoring with weighting	Score
Team's Motivation	5 %	5	0,25	
Excellence	30 %	5	1,5	
Impact	30 %	5	1,5	
Team and resources	30 %	5	1,5	
Transversal criteria	5 %	5	0,25	
Total	100 %	25	5	

Scoring system with scores 0 to 5 (no decimals).

wherein:

- 0 - Motivation Letter makes no effort to fulfill any of listed aspects
- 1 - Motivation Letter does not address all aspects or covers all aspects poorly
- 2 - Motivation Letter covers all aspects but at least half of them poorly
- 3 - Motivation Letter covers all aspects, some of which are covered poorly while others could be improved
- 4 - All aspects clearly presented but could be improved
- 5 - All aspects clearly and satisfactorily presented

Motivation Letters that receive a score 0 in one or more criteria (1 Motivation, 2 Excellence, 3 Impact, 4 Team and Resources, 5 Transversal criteria) will be automatically rejected.

Accepted Motivation Letters need to receive all together at least 50% of available scores.

Decision (accept / reject): _____

Justification in case of rejection (select one or more options)

- Several parts of the Motivation Letter are poorly addressed.
- Motivation Letter makes no effort to fulfill any of the listed aspects.
- Motivation Letter covers all aspects poorly.
- Motivation Letter covers several aspects poorly.
- The teams' motivation is not convincing enough.
- The team members are not introduced.
- The team members strengths and abilities are not adequately explained.
- We don't believe the team members will be able to work well together.
- Excellence: The foreseen approach and credibility of the proposed methodology, according to the expectations of the company is not convincing.
- Excellence: The efficiency and quality of work related to the challenge is not well explained.
- Impact: Based on the Motivation Letter we do not believe the co-creation team will find a solution that can be successful on the market.
- Impact: Based on the presented creativity of how the team predicted their future success we do not believe that the potential solution will be very innovative in regards to the existing solutions on the market.
- Impact: The co-creation team has collected none or little info about the companies' competition and poorly presented how they will try to get to a differentiated solution.
- Impact: The importance of the project for the company is poorly presented and the team hasn't foreseen the impact well.
- Team and resources: One or several of the following aspects within the team are missing: transversal, entrepreneurial, leadership skills, technical expertise, co-creation teams' ability to take a concept from ideas to market, and their capacity to carry through their ideas and understand the dynamics of the market they are trying to tap into.
- Team and resources: The foreseen time consumption (hours/team member) for the co-creation project is not well aligned with the project structure, and fitting within the 4-8 weeks time frame.
- Transversal criteria: The ideas on how to include 'Environment and low carbon economy contribution', 'Equal Opportunities, Gender balance & Diversity',

'Inclusiveness' or 'Social Impact' within the teams' way to a solution for the challenge are not included enough.

Evaluation criteria for evaluating the Motivation Letters (from co-creation teams):

(1). TEAM'S MOTIVATION (5%)

- Personal motivation: reflection of a team's enthusiasm for taking on the challenge.
- Did the team introduce the team members? (yes/no)
- Do their strengths and abilities adequately explain the reason why they are suitable? (yes/ no)
- Will they be able to work together as a team? Do they already have team cohesion?

(2). EXCELLENCE (30%):

- Soundness of the approach and credibility of the proposed methodology, according to the expectations of companies.
- Are the efficiency and quality of work related to the challenge well explained?

(3). IMPACT (30%):

- Do you believe the co-creation team will find a solution that can be successful on the market?
- To what level will the potential solution be innovative in regards to the existing solutions on the market (incremental improvement, radical improvement, breakthrough innovation, ...)? Focus on the creativity of how the team predicted their future success and not on a potential solution they might have proposed.
- Has a co-creation team already found out about the companies' competition and how they will try to get to a differentiated solution?
- How important will the project be for the company and how well did the team foresee the impact?

(4). TEAM AND RESOURCES (30%):

- Transversal, entrepreneurial and leadership skills, technical expertise, co-creation teams' ability to take a concept from ideas to market, and their capacity to carry through their ideas and understand the dynamics of the market they are trying to tap into.

- Does the team have specific resources that qualify them as a team specifically to find an excellent solution?
- Is the foreseen time consumption (hours/team member) for the co-creation project sensibly aligned with the project structure, and fitting within the 4-8 weeks time frame?

(5). TRANSVERSAL CRITERIA (5%):

- Does a co-creation team have ideas on how to include 'Environment and low carbon economy contribution', 'Equal Opportunities, Gender balance & Diversity', 'Inclusiveness' or 'Social Impact' within their way to a solution for the challenge?

ANNEX 11 : Template for Evaluation: Solutions

Title of Challenge:

Company:

Co-creation Team:

Criteria (same for INDUSAC Evaluation Board and for companies):

Table 5 : Criteria and scoring system for evaluating Solutions.

Evaluation criteria	Weighting	Max scoring	Max scoring with weighting	Score	Evaluator
Deliverable quality	30 %	10	3		company
Business performance indicators / Technical performance indicators	60 %	10	6		company
Deadline compliance	10 %	10	1		INDUSAC
Total	100 %	30	10		

Scoring system with scores 0 to 10 (no decimals).

wherein:

- 0 - no effort made to fulfill any of listed aspects
- 1-2 - some aspects were not covered or all aspects were covered poorly
- 3-4 - all aspects covered but at least half of them poorly
- 5-6 - all aspects covered, some of which are covered poorly while others could be improved
- 7-8 - all aspects clearly presented but could be improved
- 9-10 - all aspects clearly and satisfactorily presented

Students from co-creation teams with solutions scoring above the threshold (7 points) will receive payment.

Decision: _____

Justification for the company to describe the deliverable quality (select one option)

- Approve the solution: The submitted deliverables are of excellent and of very high quality.
- Approve the solution: The submitted deliverables are of high quality.
- Approve the solution: The submitted deliverables are of acceptable quality.

Reject the solution: The submitted deliverables are of very low and unacceptable quality.

ANNEX 12 : Notifications that Companies Receive from the Platform

NOTE: draft messages below may include dates, which need to be adjusted to appropriate cut-off dates.

Confirmation to Companies of Submission of a Challenge

When a company submits a Challenge for a review it gets an automatic email:

Dear Sir or Madam,

Thank you for submitting a Challenge on behalf of your company. Your Challenge is being reviewed by INDUSAC administrators. You will be notified about the progress.

Best regards,

INDUSAC partners

Notification to Companies about Published Challenges

When a Challenge is published, the company gets an automatic email:

Dear Sir or Madam,

The Challenge <title of the Challenge> you submitted on behalf of your company <name of company> has been approved and published on the INDUSAC website <embedded or added link to the website>

INDUSAC partners and other participating organisations (public universities and research institutions) will be promoting it through different media and channels among students and researchers.

We will be collecting applications / Motivation Letters from student / researcher co-creation teams until 31.01.2024. In February 2024 you will be asked to select one or more co-creation team(s) that you wish to work with (as indicated in your Challenge).

In case of questions, please consult the FAQ section <embed or add link> or contact us at [indusac\(at\)ijs.si](mailto:indusac(at)ijs.si).

*Best regards,
INDUSAC partners*

Notification to Companies about Received Motivation Letters

When the INDUSAC Evaluation Board has completed pre-selection, links to selected Motivation Letters are sent to the respective company for evaluation, along with instructions on how to select the co-creation team via the INDUSAC platform:

Dear Sir or Madam,

The INDUSAC has received solution proposals (Motivation Letters) for your Challenge. You may access the Motivation Letters at the following links

<links to Motivation Letters>

Please review the Motivation Letters and when finished, proceed to select on the INDUSAC platform the co-creation team(s) who will be solving your Challenge no later than 23.02.2024. Further instructions are on the platform (Annex 10).

In case of questions, please consult the FAQ section (<embed or add link>) or contact us at [indusac\(at\)ijs.si](mailto:indusac(at)ijs.si).

*Best regards,
INDUSAC partners*

Notification to companies that the FSTP declaration has been Signed

Dear Sir or Madam,

Thank you for selecting a co-creation team. We would like to inform you that the administrative procedures with the co-creation team have been completed. You may now get in contact with the co-creation team and arrange the kick-off meeting.

Please follow this [link](#) to a private chat with the co-creation team. This is the [link](#) to the INDUSAC library where you will find templates to assist the team in preparing the deliverables and a To-Do list (a Mentoring Plan) that the team may use as guidance to solve the Challenge.

The team may start working on a Challenge and should submit their Solution no later than 02.05.2024.

In case of questions please check FAQ or send an e-mail to [indusac\(at\)ijs.si](mailto:indusac(at)ijs.si).

Best regards,

INDUSAC partners

Notification to Companies to Evaluate the Solution and Fill out the Questionnaire

Once a co-creation team submits a Solution, the company is notified via the platform to evaluate the Solution and fill out the questionnaire:

Dear Sir or Madam,

The co-creation team has delivered a solution for your challenge <title of Challenge>. Please find the uploaded documents here <links to Solution>.

We ask you to review the documents and give feedback. Further instructions are on the platform (Annex 11).

We also ask you to fill in the <satisfaction questionnaire>

We would like to receive your feedback no later than 15.5.2024.

In case of questions, please consult the FAQ section (<embed or add link>) or contact us at [indusac\(at\)ijs.si](mailto:indusac@ijs.si).

Best regards,

INDUSAC partners

ANNEX 13 : Notifications that Students and Researchers Receive from the Platform

NOTE: draft messages below may include dates, which need to be adjusted to appropriate cut-off dates.

Team-member confirmation of Motivation Letter and participation in the co-creation team (for students and researchers)

Once a student/researcher starts to prepare a Motivation Letter, two checkpoints are made before submission: (1) the student/researcher needs to be registered on the INDUSAC platform, and (2) once registered, the student/researcher needs to assemble a co-creation team in order to be able to submit a Motivation Letter. Notifications covering these instances are listed below:

Dear Co-creation Team Member,

Your team leader has submitted the Motivation Letter for the Challenge <Challenge title> for your approval.

Please review and confirm the Motivation Letter and your participation in this co-creation team no later than: 31.01.2024. Until you have approved the Motivation Letter, it cannot be submitted to INDUSAC.

In case of questions, please consult the FAQ section (<embed or add link>) or contact us at [indusac\(at\)ijs.si](mailto:indusac(at)ijs.si).

Best regards,

INDUSAC partners

Team members invite other students / researchers do join the co-creation team

Dear <recipient name>,

I'm putting together a co-creation team of students/researchers that is applying to solve a Challenge _____ (Title of the Challenge) from company _____ (name of the company) from _____ (country). For details, please click here:

_____ (insert the link to the Challenge) and I would like to have you as a teammate.

Would you like to join the international team of students and researchers to solve a Challenge? Please, register here.

Official call for students/researchers and all the terms are published in the INDUSAC website: <https://indusac.eu/>.

Kind regards,

Notification to Students/Researchers of Receipt of Motivation Letter

Once the last co-creation team member confirms the Motivation Letter, all co-creation team members receive an e-mail:

*Dear Co-creation Team Member,
Thank you for submitting your Motivation Letter to the Challenge <Challenge title> as part of the co-creation team comprising <name of team leader>, <name of member #1>, and <name of member #2>!*

Please click on the link below to confirm the Motivation Letter: <link>

After the submission deadline, your Motivation Letter will be revised. You will be notified about the result by 01.03.2024, at which time you will also receive instructions on how to proceed.

In case of questions, please consult the FAQ section (<embed or add link>) or contact us at indusac(at)ijs.si.

*Best regards,
INDUSAC partners*

Notification of Students/Researchers about the Approval or Rejection of Motivation Letter

a) If the Motivation Letter has been Accepted

*Dear Co-creation Team Members,
INDUSAC is happy to inform you that your Motivation Letter to the Challenge <Challenge title> has been accepted by the company. The student members of your team may proceed to signing a Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP) Declaration. This declaration outlines the formal aspect of the financial support for students. The FSTP declaration needs to be signed digitally within seven (7) days from receiving this message. Please follow this <link> to fill in the data (bank details, etc.) and sign the document.*

Once the FSTP Declaration is signed by all student members of the co-creation team, no later than 07.03.2024, all co-creation team members and the company will be notified with the timeline. You may then get in contact with the company and arrange the kick-off meeting.

In case of questions please check FAQ or send an e-mail to indusac(at)ijs.si.

*Best regards,
INDUSAC partners*

b) If the Motivation Letter has been Rejected

*Dear Co-creation Team Members,
INDUSAC regrets to inform you that your Motivation Letter to the Challenge <Challenge title> has not been approved. Please find below the justification:*

<justification (see Annex 10)>

You are welcome to submit further Motivation Letters, as per the rules set out in the Call for Students and Researchers, by the next cut-off date. The available Challenges can be found at the following website: indusac.eu.

In case of questions please check FAQ or send an e-mail to indusac@ijs.si.

*Best regards,
INDUSAC partners*

Invitation to Students to Sign a FSTP Declaration

*Dear Co-creation Team Members,
Please proceed to signing a Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP) Declaration. This declaration outlines the formal aspect of the financial support for students. The FSTP declaration needs to be signed digitally within seven (7) days from receiving this message and no later than 07.03.2024. Please follow this <link> to fill in the data (bank details, etc.) and sign the document.*

Once the FSTP Declaration is signed by all student members of the co-creation team, all co-creation team members and the company will be notified with the timeline. You may then get in contact with the company and arrange the kick-off meeting.

In case of questions please check FAQ or send an e-mail to indusac@ijs.si.

*Best regards,
INDUSAC partners*

Confirmation for Students that the FSTP Declaration has been Signed

*Dear Co-creation Team Members,
Thank you for signing the FSTP Declaration. You may now get in contact with the company and arrange the kick-off meeting.*

Please follow this <link> to a private chat with the company. On this <link> is the INDUSAC library where you will find templates to assist you in preparing the deliverables and a To-Do list (a Mentoring Plan) that you may use as guidance to solve the Challenge.

Please start working on a Challenge and submit your Solution no later than 02.05.2024.

In case of questions please check FAQ or send an e-mail to indusac@ijs.si.

*Best regards,
INDUSAC partners*

Notification to Students/Researchers about Deadline for Submission of Solution

If solutions have not been submitted one week before the deadline, co-creation team members receive the following email:

*Dear Co-creation Team Members,
This is a kind reminder that you have to submit your solution and the Co-creation Implementation Report in one week's time.
In case of questions please check FAQ or send an e-mail to [indusac\(at\)ijs.si](mailto:indusac(at)ijs.si).
Best regards,
INDUSAC partners*

ANNEX 14 : Skill Level Survey for Students/Researchers before the Project

Questions for co-creation team members upon receiving info about positive selection (before the start of the co-creation project):

Please, evaluate your current level of the following soft skills (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - **Likert Scale**):

- Communication skills
- Negotiation
- Results oriented thinking
- Responsibility
- Creativity
- Planning skills
- Analytical thinking
- Critical thinking
- Conflict management
- Tolerance and acceptance for different approaches
- Common goal definition
- Time management and effective planning
- Leadership
- Teamwork
- Experience in working with companies
- Understanding for international colleagues
- English

Selection (Multiple choice)

- Which skills would you like to develop/improve:
 - Communication skills
 - Negotiation
 - Results oriented thinking

- Responsibility
- Creativity
- Planning skills
- Analytical thinking
- Critical thinking
- Conflict management
- Tolerance and acceptance for different approaches
- Common goal definition
- Time management and effective planning
- Leadership
- Teamwork
- Experience in working with companies
- Understanding for international colleagues
- English

Yes/no questions

Are you familiar with the following methods:

- SWOT analysis
- Persona Method
- Utility analysis
- Trend analysis
- Scenario analysis
- Cost-benefit analyses
- Product portfolio analysis / BCG Matrix
- White spot analysis
- Creating marketing strategies
- Value proposition analysis
- Developing a business plan

- Preparation of business model canvas
- Building a Product Service System
- Detecting ideas
- Empathy map
- Kano-method
- Building prototypes
- Simulation model
- Virtual prototype
- Target group analysis

ANNEX 15 : Questionnaire for Students/Researchers after Completion of the Co-creation Project

The purpose of the questionnaire is to evaluate the level of upskilling achieved during the co-creation project.

Questions for students/researchers after submission of the final report

Please, evaluate your current level of the following soft skills (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - **Likert Scale**):

- Communication skills
- Negotiation
- Results oriented thinking
- Responsibility
- Creativity
- Planning skills
- Analytical thinking
- Critical thinking
- Conflict management
- Tolerance and acceptance for different approaches
- Common goal definition
- Time management and effective planning
- Leadership
- Teamwork
- Experience in working with companies
- Understanding for international colleagues
- English

Selection (Multiple choice)

- Which skills were significantly developed / improved through the co-creation team project:

- Communication skills
- Negotiation
- Results oriented thinking
- Responsibility
- Creativity
- Planning skills
- Analytical thinking
- Critical thinking
- Conflict management
- Tolerance and acceptance for different approaches
- Common goal definition
- Time management and effective planning
- Leadership
- Teamwork
- Experience in working with companies
- Understanding for international colleagues
- English

Yes/no questions

Are you familiar with the following methods:

- SWOT analysis
- Persona Method
- Utility analysis
- Trend analysis
- Scenario analysis
- Cost-benefit analyses
- Product portfolio analysis / BCG Matrix
- White spot analysis

- Creating marketing strategies
- Value proposition analysis
- Developing a business plan
- Preparation of business model canvas
- Building a Product Service System
- Detecting ideas
- Empathy map
- Kano-method
- Building prototypes
- Simulation model
- Virtual prototype
- Target group analysis

Please, evaluate your experience in terms of clarity and satisfaction with the process (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - **Likert Scale**):

Topic	clarity of the process	satisfaction
finding the detailed information about the Challenge		
user-friendliness of the use of the platform (user experience of the online platform)		
method assistance through explanations and templates		
assistance through the proposed process and milestones		

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Topic	clarity of the process	satisfaction
registration on the platform		
creation of a team		
timeline of challenge application process		
timeline for solving the challenge		
submission of application / Motivation Letter		
working in a team - with other students / researchers		
working in a team - with company		
preparation of deliverables (solution, reports, etc.)		
submission of deliverables (solution, reports, etc.)		
(students only) financial transaction process		

Any general comments? (text answer) _____

Collaboration

How often did you meet the company representative?

1) Never 2) once or twice 3) bi-weekly 4) weekly 5) more often

Which communication channel did you use?

1) INDUSAC platform 2) Slack 3) WhatsApp or similar Messenger 4) E-Mail 5) Online meeting platform (e.g. teams, zoom) 6) other please specify: _____

How often did you meet with your team members?

1) Never 2) once or twice 3) bi-weekly 4) weekly 5) more often

Which communication channel did you use?

1) INDUSAC platform 2) Slack 3) WhatsApp or similar Messenger 4) E-Mail 5) Online meeting platform (e.g. teams, zoom) 6) other please specify: _____

Did you benefit from working in a multicultural team?

1) Not at all 2) a bit 3) neutral 4) Yes I did 5) Yes a lot

Rate the level of agreement or disagreement with each statement on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 represents "Strongly Disagree" and 5 represents "Strongly Agree."

- The co-creation mechanism encouraged active participation and engagement from all participants.
- The co-creation process encouraged collaboration and co-learning among the participants.
- The co-creation process incorporated customer research and insights to understand the end-users' needs and preferences.
- The co-creation process fostered interdisciplinary collaboration, integrating perspectives from social sciences and humanities to other disciplines.
- We, as a team, were encouraged to explore ethical considerations and social impact when generating ideas during the co-creation process.
- I was able to participate equally in the decision-making process.

- The co-creation process resulted in solutions that specifically addressed gender-related issues or considerations.
- Overall, the co-creation process successfully prioritised the human aspect (Inclusivity, Gender dimension, Interdisciplinarity, User Perspective, Collaboration, Iterative Feedback, Ethical Considerations) and created a meaningful and inclusive environment.

Any general comments? (text answer)_____

Please, evaluate your current level of agreement with the following statements (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - **Likert Scale**) + option “I didn’t use it”:

- Help desk assistance (e.g. value of support received) was adequate.
- It is likely you would recommend participation in such a program to other peers
- Challenges were diverse enough and you were able to find an interesting one fast and start the co-creation process
- The Challenges were well described.
- Companies’ expectations were reasonable.
- You are satisfied with the results that your co-creation team submitted,
- You benefited from working in an international environment.

Open questions:

- Appropriateness of funding: did you find funding appropriate, high enough? Were you able to cover all your costs? Considering actual costs and given rational consideration, do you feel that the funding received would be sufficient for supporting more than one co-creation project?
- What is the main reason you applied to INDUSAC open calls (money, connections to students and/or companies/researchers, international experiences, new skills etc.)?
- How would you rate your experience with the provided method recommendations and explanations, templates, process and milestone recommendations?

Tick a box Yes / No:

Would you like the INDUSAC communication team to prepare a success story / a good practice story based on your project and results? If so, the communication team will contact you for more information.

ANNEX 16 : Questionnaire for Companies after completion of the Co-creation Project

Questions for company representatives after submission of the final report

Satisfaction with following steps of the whole process (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - **Likert Scale** + option “I didn’t use it”)

- publishing the challenge
- registration on the platform
- user-friendliness of the use of the platform (user experience of the online platform)
- experience of the offline modules (support material and libraries) of the platform
- communication with the co-creation team
- adequateness of timeline between posting and start of challenge
- adequateness of timeline for solving the challenge
- revision of applications / motivation letters
- assisting co-creation team in carrying out the project
- preparation of deliverables, reports, etc.
- submission of deliverables, reports, etc.
- punctuality of deliverable submission

Any general comments? (text answer)_____

Satisfaction with the solution and work of the co-creation team (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - **Likert Scale**)

- Technical performance indicators:
 - Innovativeness: How do you estimate the innovative potential of the solution?
 - Creativity: How do you evaluate the creativity of the solution?
 - Improvement: How do you evaluate the performance of the solution compared with your actual/previous solution (if not existent with a competitor’s solution)?
- Business performance indicators:
 - Market potential: How do you evaluate the market potential of the solution?
 - Relevancy: How do you evaluate the relevance of the solution?
- Quality
 - Soundness: How do you evaluate the soundness of the work of the co-creation team?
 - Quality of work: How do you evaluate the quality of the work of the co-creation team?
 - Satisfaction: How satisfied are you with the work of the co-creation team?

- Will you follow up on the solution provided by the co-creation team within your company (No, definitely not – probably not – not decided yet – yes we will – yes, we already started)?

Tick a box Yes / No:

Have all requested deliverables been delivered by the co-creation team?

Tick a box Yes / No:

Would you like the INDUSAC communication team to prepare a success story / a good practice story based on your project and results? If so, the communication team will contact you for more information.

**STATEMENT ON
NON-DISCLOSURE OF INFORMATION
AND IMPARTIALITY**

This statement pertains to procedures and activities carried out within the INDUSAC project.

This is to certify that I, the undersigned:

<Name and Surname>

<Home Address>

<Post Number and Town / City>

<State / Country>,

employed at:

<organisation>

member of the INDUSAC consortium

undertake that I shall not disclose confidential information (such as applications, work results, and personal data in connection to the INDUSAC piloting), acquired through activities within the INDUSAC Committee(s), through gathering and processing of data related to companies' and personal information regarding co-creation team applications, their work and their results, to unauthorised persons.

I hereby also confirm that I am not giving preferential treatment in regards to Motivation Letters Challenges / Solutions based on the applicant's professional or personal connections with INDUSAC partners and that approval is based solely on the quality of the Motivation Letters / Challenges / Solutions.

The obligations stated herein shall remain in force for a term of seven (7) years as from the date of signing hereof, and may be prolonged if the activities concerning the confidential data, as defined in this statement, continue after the expiration of this period.

This statement has been signed in 2 (two) identical paper copies, where one is for the signatory and one for the INDUSAC coordinator. The statement can be signed also electronically.

Place _____, date _____

Signature: _____

ANNEX 18 : INDUSAC Declaration of Financial Support to Third Parties

**INDUSAC DECLARATION
on Financial Support to Third Parties**

We, the undersigned,

Co-creation Team member 1 (student)

Name

Family name

Address

Citizenship or residency

Gender

E-mail

Month / year of study start

Name of public university where you study

Country of the university

Bank Details

Bank Name and Address

Transaction Account

IBAN

SWIFT Code of Bank

Co-creation Team member 2 (student)

Name

Family name

Address

Citizenship or residency

Gender

E-mail

Month / year of study start

Name of public university where you study

Country of the university

Bank Details

Bank Name and Address

Transaction Account

IBAN

SWIFT Code of Bank

Co-creation Team member 3 (student)

Name

Family name

Address

Citizenship or residency

Gender

E-mail

Month / year of study start

Name of public university where you study

Country of the university

Bank Details

Bank Name and Address

Transaction Account

IBAN

SWIFT Code of Bank

additional Co-creation Team members (students)

xx

xx

xx

hereby declare that:

- we have established a cooperation, within the Horizon Europe INDUSAC project, with the INDUSAC project coordinator, Jožef Stefan Institute, Jamova cesta 39, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia, with the intention of solving a Challenge entitled <Title of the Challenge> issued by a company <company name> within a time frame of 4-8 weeks;
- we comprise a co-creation team represented by a co-creation team leader and at least two additional student/researchers, wherein all members of the co-creation team share equal treatment and responsibilities;
- the co-creation team, in addition to the listed students, comprises the following researchers as well:
_____;
- we accept the terms and conditions of the Call for Students and Researchers published on the INDUSAC website
- we accept the financial support to third parties, provided by the INDUSAC project coordinator, and in the amount of up to 3,000 EUR gross per co-creation team and up to 1,000 EUR gross per individual student, based on financial support eligibility terms listed in the Call for Students and Researchers

The declaration shall enter into force on the date on which it is signed by all parties.

The declaration must be signed digitally.

Place, date _____

Name of co-creation Team Member 1 (student)

Place, date _____

Name of co-creation Team Member 2 (student)

Place, date _____

Name of co-creation Team Member 3 (student)

ANNEX 19 : TO DO List / Mentoring Plan Example

Example of a Mentoring Plan:

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Task title	Input	Task description	Output / Deliverable	Deadline / Date	Template/Method	Process Phases Overview	
Get to know your team, the company and the challenge	Kick-Off with Company	Company details, Product introduction, Task description, Expectations	The company will present itself in a format they decide to give you an insight into the company history, its organisational structure, its product, or service portfolio and why they applied for this project. For your better understanding, the company's expectations and a task description will be presented with a Q&A session to ensure a clear understanding.	Clear understanding of the challenge		Phase 1	
1. Warm up				Week 1		Phase 2	
1.1 Internal team assignment to tasks	To do list, INDUSAC list of methods and tools	Analyse the to-dos necessary to solve the challenge. Assign teammates to tasks. Consider that for some tasks the company that hosts your challenge needs to be involved. Make sure to plan these tasks/ feedback rounds early on in the process.	Assignment of teammates to tasks; Scheduling of major tasks/ feedback with company (invites sent out/ appointments made)	Week 1		Phase 3	
1.2 Technical Set-Up	INDUSAC Platform	Set up a place where you can work together collaboratively. You may just share a folder on e.g. Google Drive and send the link within the INDUSAC chat to your teammates and the company representative. The company may also have an online storage space that can be used for your collaborative work that they can provide. If they ask you to use their offer, make sure to do so, since it might be due to data protection regulations.	Shared Workspaces (e.g. Google Drive folder)	Week 1			
1.3 Get to know the Company	Company's Website, Company's Input Materials	First, visit the website and try to find out the following: (Main facts about the company (founding year, employees, national/international)? What is the company selling (products, services...)? What kind of products/services is it (high involvement, low involvement, utilitarian, hedonic)? Which market is the company targeting (mass market, niche market)? Who is the main target of the product/service and is the target group aware of the product/service?)		Week 1			
Let's tackle the challenge				Week 1 and 2			
2.1 Identify the product	Product description from the company, Research results	This task is for your understanding. To get to know the product you are working on, read through all provided material from the company. Further do research on the internet or ask your acquaintances if they know or even used the product. You can also use the information you gathered in 1.3. Within this task, you can be creative with the visualization. Use all tools you want to e.g. Miro, OneNote, Mind maps or posters. Make sure every team member has access to the used tool.	Visualization of the product	Week 1			
2.2 Determine the properties	Technical description of the product (if provided by the company you may use it)	Create a list of relevant technical aspects such as the material, the size, and the weight. Look at all the components and try to understand how the technical properties match the function. If the company provides such a list you can use it. If you search on the internet make sure to use the right product variant. You can also implement the technical details in your output from 2.1.	Excel file with technical product details (product properties)	Week 2			
2.3 Research and Comparison	Product reviews, Consumer reports, Experts	Look at customer feedback and reviews to see what customers are saying about the product. This can give you insight into any issues or concerns that customers have with the product. You can ask the company if they provide you with a contact person for the marketing or sales office. Compare the product with similar products on the market. This will help you understand how the product stacks up against the competition. Through this task, you should find out if products from competitors have product properties that might be relevant for the company that hosts the challenge too.	Excel file with customer review compared to similar products	Week 2			
Milestone 1	Current findings	Present your findings to your company representative to make sure early on in the process, that you understood the product properties of the product that you focus on.	Feedback on current findings	End of Week 2		Phase 4	
M.1.1 Generate concept for milestone presentation	Current findings	Prepare a structured concept (one pager) which describes how you will present your current findings and next steps at the milestone.	One pager with concept for milestone presentation				
M.1.2 Preparation of milestone presentation	Concept for milestone presentation, Current Findings	Preparation of milestone presentation and make sure the product properties are presented correctly and in an understandable way. If you want to present your Excel, put them in a ppt format to assure a smooth presentation.	PPT Milestone Presentation				
M.1.3 Dry run of pitch	PPT Milestone presentation	Train the presentation for the milestone and give constructive feedback by your team members to improve the presentation style and the slide deck. After your feedback revise your slide deck and assure to know the presentation and present it to the company representatives.	Be ready for Milestone				
M.1.4 Revising presentation and current findings	Feedback on Milestone Presentation	Milestone presentation After the presentation, the company will give you feedback in oral/written form. If it is oral, please assure that (at least) one team member is writing everything down. Incorporate feedback into your final deliverables.	New input for next steps (potential) revisions and rework	Week 3			
Let's explore the future				Week 3			
3.1 Find out if your company provided you with scenarios	Scenarios	If the company has already identified scenarios, they will provide them to you and you can use them as a basis for analysis. Analyse the trends as well, and compare your findings with the provided scenarios. Make sure you have received them within the INDUSAC chat or in your shared workspace.	Information on basis of challenge. Scenarios provided/ verify	Week 3			

3.2 Analyzing trends and scenarios	Scenarios	Inform yourself in detail about the scenarios the company provided. First, analyze them and focus on the changes compared to the current situation. Then, compare them with the scenarios you have developed. For example, a "passenger car" could be that the target customer is not a private customer but, for example, a tax company. Discuss the findings with your group. How can the product be improved to fit into the different scenarios? What is relevant for the customer in the future? How does it affect the product in a technical way (e.g. load on the clutch and engine is different because customers do not care about the vehicle)? Write down your findings in tabular form. Research current trends using either one of the proposed websites or any other resource of trends that you might know. For your information you might need to be aware of the fact that the current version of the product is not relevant for the future. The current version is looking for a tax company. Focus on 5-6 trends you consider most relevant for the product or brand of interest. Please make sure to also include an explanation of why you consider these trends to be the most relevant. Have you already noticed the trends? How would you act as a company knowing these trends?	Week 3	Excel or PowerPoint table with current and future scenarios based on developments based on scenarios	Scenario and Trend analysis method and template
3.2.2 For teams with scenarios as tabs	Scenarios	Research current trends using either one of the proposed websites or any other resource of trends that you might know. For your information you might need to be aware of the fact that the current version of the product is not relevant for the future. The current version is looking for a tax company. Focus on 5-6 trends you consider most relevant for the product or brand of interest. Please make sure to also include an explanation of why you consider these trends to be the most relevant. Have you already noticed the trends? How would you act as a company knowing these trends?	Week 3	Excel or PowerPoint table with current and future scenarios based on developments based on scenarios	Scenario and Trend analysis method and template, e.g. best versions of https://www.itsmo.com/reading/brand-adjar
3.2.2 For teams with trends as tabs	Scenarios	Research current trends using either one of the proposed websites or any other resource of trends that you might know. For your information you might need to be aware of the fact that the current version of the product is not relevant for the future. The current version is looking for a tax company. Focus on 5-6 trends you consider most relevant for the product or brand of interest. Please make sure to also include an explanation of why you consider these trends to be the most relevant. Have you already noticed the trends? How would you act as a company knowing these trends?	Week 3	Excel or PowerPoint table with current and future scenarios based on developments based on scenarios	Scenario and Trend analysis method and template, e.g. best versions of https://www.itsmo.com/reading/brand-adjar
Milestone 2	Current findings	Present your selected scenarios/trends as a starting point of your results to your company representative in an understandable way.	End of Week 3	Feedback on current findings	
M 2.1 Generate concept presentation	Current findings	Prepare a structured concept (one pager) which describes how you will present your results of scenarios and next steps at the milestone.	Week 4	One pager with concept for milestone presentation	
M 2.2 Preparation of milestone presentation	Concept for milestone presentation	Preparation of milestone presentation and make sure the product properties are presented correctly and in an understandable way. Present the possible development directions of the product (optional) regarding the scenarios or trends. Because this topic is more creative, you can choose a format you think fits best to give an understanding of your outcome.	Week 4	Excel, PowerPoint, Minio...	
M 2.3 Dry run of pitch	Current Findings	Train the presentation for the milestone and give constructive feedback to your team members to improve the presentation style and the slide deck.	Week 4	Be ready for Milestone presentation	
M 2.4 Revising presentation and current findings	Presentation format you chose in M 2.2	After your feedback revise your slide deck and assure to incorporate everything down. Incorporate feedback into your final deliverables.	Week 4	New input for next steps (potential) revises and rework	
4. Deduct future-robust product properties	Feedback on Milestone presentation	After the presentation, the company will give you feedback in oral/written form. If it is oral, please assure that (at least) one team member is writing everything down. Incorporate feedback into your final deliverables.	Week 4		
4.1 Deduct future-robust product properties from your findings	CS, Excel or PowerPoint with current product specifications and future developments	Devolve with the information you collected on relevant trends (and/or scenarios) further product requirements. From these, you should derive product properties that are relevant in the context of each trend (scenario). Product properties are the characteristics of a product, while product requirements are the wanted characteristics by the customers. The product properties that are derived in the context of scenarios or trends can be seen as future-robust product properties if they appear in more than one scenario. How is the product specified down and what are the product properties that you now consider relevant for future-robust product properties? For example, a tax company. A possible future-robust product property would be the "possibility to insert separation between the driver and the passengers". What are the future-robust product properties that can be derived from the trends or scenarios? To evaluate these properties create an Excel with all trends/scenarios. Insert all product properties and mark by which trend they are affected. With this, you can select the future-robust ones.	Week 4	Excel file	
4.2 Prioritize future-robust product properties	Excel or PowerPoint with product properties	With this future-robust product properties, conduct a cost-benefit analysis to prioritize the product properties. Within this analysis, your team collaborates online by which the properties should be ranked. This will help you prioritize the properties. Therefore, you can use an Excel file.	Week 4	Excel file	
Final Milestone	Final results	The aim of this presentation is to show your results in an understandable way and to show the company your hard work and why it is so good.	Week 4	Feedback on final results	
FM 1 Generate concept for milestone presentation	Final results	Prepare a structured concept (one pager) which describes how you will present your results of the derived future-robust properties and how you derived them out of scenarios or trends (depending on 3.2). Think of how you can present your future-robust product properties from your findings in a way the company understands them, their relevance and how you came to them.	Week 4	One pager with concept for milestone presentation	
FM 2 Revising concept of milestone presentation	Concept for milestone presentation	Train the presentation for the milestone and give constructive feedback to your team members to improve the presentation style and the slide deck. Incorporate feedback into your final deliverables.	Week 4	Excel, PowerPoint, Minio...	
FM 3 Dry run of pitch	Final results	Train the presentation for the milestone and give constructive feedback to your team members to improve the presentation style and the slide deck. Incorporate feedback into your final deliverables.	Week 4	Be ready for Milestone presentation	
FM 4 Revising presentation results	Presentation format you chose in FM 2	After your feedback revise your slide deck and assure to know the presentation and present it to the company representatives.	Week 4	Revised presentation and results	
5. Final submission	Feedback on Milestone presentation	Milestone presentation After the final presentation, the company will give you feedback in oral/written form. If it is oral, please assure that (at least) one team member is writing everything down. Incorporate feedback into your final deliverables.	Week 5		
5.1 Submit solution	Final results, Report	Upload your deliverables on the INDUSAC platform in the respective space for it. If you have not yet written a report about the process, please do so and upload it with the other deliverables. In case you have files, that are too big to be uploaded, talk to the company and tell them where within the shared workspace you have to upload the deliverables. Please only do so if the upload on the INDUSAC platform in the respective fields is not possible.	Week 5	Deliverables on INDUSAC platform	2 days after final presentation

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